

101136318 – SUSTAIN-HTA
Support Utilisation of Sustainable and
TAIlored INnovative methods for HTA

D1.1 – Taxonomy report

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	D1.1 Taxonomy report		
	WP1 – Identification, Synthesis & Prioritisation		Version: V1.2
	Authors: Saif Elayan, Shane Collins, Jamie Elvidge, Karen Facey, Zoe Garrett, Wim Goettsch, Wija Oortwijn, and Liza van Mun		Dissemination: PU

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DOCUMENT HISTORY

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V1.0	20 May 2024	First Draft
V1.1	04 June 2024	Second Draft for Steering Committee review
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DEFINITIONS

Partners of the SUSTAIN-HTA Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

1. **UU** Universiteit Utrecht (Netherlands)
2. **UB** Università Commerciale Luigi Bocconi (Italy)
3. **EMC** Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam (Netherlands)
4. **ZIN** Zorginstituut Nederland (Netherlands)
5. **RUMC** Stichting Radboud Universitair Medisch Centrum (Netherlands)
6. **SRI** Syreon Kutato Intezet Korlatolt Felelossegu Tarsasag (Hungary)
7. **OSTEBA** Fundacion Vasca de Innovacion e Investigacion Sanitarias (Spain)
8. **GetReal I** GetReal Institute (Netherlands)
9. **SYNAPSE** Synapse Research Management Partners (Spain)
10. **NIPN** Nemzeti Nepegészségügyi és Gyógyszerészeti Központ (Hungary)
11. **AGE.NA.S** Agenzia Nazionale per i Servizi Sanitari Regionali (Italy)
12. **AQUAS** Agencia de Qualitat i Avaluació Sanitaries de Catalunya (Spain)
13. **NOMA** Statens Legemiddelverk (Norway)
14. **UCSC** Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (Italy)
15. **NICE** National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (United Kingdom)

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the European Health and Digital Executive Agency for the undertaking of the SUSTAIN-HTA project (101136318).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The SUSTAIN-HTA Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst SUSTAIN-HTA partners for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
CEA	Cost-Effectiveness Assessment
EMA	The European Medicines Agency
EU	European Union
EUnetHTA	The European Network for Health Technology Assessment
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
HTACG	Member State Coordination Group on HTA
REA	Relative Effectiveness Assessment

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document reports on the development of the SUSTAIN-HTA taxonomy tool (Task 1.2). The tool aims to standardise terminology and establish a uniform language within the project, thereby enhancing communication and collaboration among SUSTAIN-HTA stakeholders and ensuring clear, consistent dissemination of outputs. The development process began with a targeted search for relevant documents on Health Technology Assessment (HTA) methodologies and regulations within the European Union (EU). Identified documents were reviewed, and relevant terms appearing therein were extracted and documented. Definitions were then sourced either directly from these documents or from existing glossaries and published literature. The workgroup thoroughly reviewed all terms and their definitions, selecting those most relevant to the project for inclusion. These terms were organised alphabetically in a glossary and categorised within a taxonomic scheme. The taxonomy tool, detailed in this document, will be updated annually to remain current with the project's progress and implementation of the EU HTA Regulation. The tool is available in document and web-based formats to enhance usability and navigation.

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1. Introduction

HTA is a multidisciplinary process that uses explicit methods to determine the value of a health technology at different points in its lifecycle. The purpose is to inform decision-making in order to promote an equitable, efficient, and high-quality health system. HTA methodologies and processes are constantly evolving to address the emergence of new, increasingly complex health technologies and changes in health system delivery. Moreover, the implementation of HTA varies considerably across countries and regions, reflecting differences in healthcare systems, priorities, regulatory environments, and political, social, and economic contexts. These dynamics—multidisciplinary involvement, fast-paced evolution, and variability in implementation—collectively contribute to issues of inconsistencies and a lack of clarity in HTA terminology, which poses challenges for effective communication and collaboration in the field.

Recognising these issues, the SUSTAIN-HTA project has developed a taxonomy tool to standardise terminology and establish a uniform language across all project activities. The tool includes a comprehensive glossary of terms complemented by a taxonomic scheme that categorises these terms based on their associations with established assessment elements of HTA, as well as regulatory and decision-making processes. This tool facilitates effective communication and collaboration among stakeholders involved in SUSTAIN-HTA and ensures consistent and clear dissemination of the project’s outputs to a broader audience. We perceive this tool as a living resource, continually updated and refined to address evolving project needs and developments in the field.

2. Methods

The development of the taxonomy tool commenced with a targeted search for reports, websites, official documents, and guidelines addressing the methodological aspects of, and regulations on, HTA in the context of the EU. Several documents were identified, including reports from the European Network for Health Technology Assessment (EUnetHTA), guidelines from the Member State Coordination Group on HTA (HTACG), EU legislative documents (regulations, directives, decisions, recommendations), and articles and reports from the European Medicines Agency (EMA) website. Each document was reviewed to identify relevant terms, which were then recorded in a Microsoft Excel workbook. The frequency of term appearances was noted to guide the inclusion of terms in the tool. Additional details such as synonyms, acronyms, variants, alternative spellings, and source references were also documented.

Definitions for these candidate terms were primarily sourced from the original documents in which they appeared and the well-known HTA glossary (<https://htaglossary.net>). When definitions were unavailable in these sources, we referred to existing glossaries from other European projects (e.g., IMI GetReal, IMI Adapt Smart, IMI PREFER) and domain-specific glossaries, such as the “Glossary of Health Economics Terms” and the “NCI Dictionary of Cancer Terms.” For terms with multiple definitions, all definitions were documented for further review by the workgroup. There were no instances where a term lacked a definition. Additional candidate terms identified during this phase were also included for consideration.

The workgroup analysed the list of candidate terms and their definitions, assigning each a status of either “Core” or “Non-core.” “Core” terms were deemed highly relevant, whereas “Non-core” terms were excluded at this stage due to their general nature or expected limited use within the project.

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The workgroup evaluated each definition for clarity and relevance to HTA practices in the EU. For terms with multiple definitions, the workgroup selected the most suitable one. In instances where any term lacked an adequate definition, alternative definitions were suggested by the workgroup and adopted after discussion. The finalised list of terms and definitions was then arranged alphabetically in a glossary.

Using this glossary of terms, a flat taxonomic scheme was developed based on the work from Task 1.4. This scheme classified the terms into categories related to established HTA assessment elements: Relative Effectiveness Assessment (REA), Cost-Effectiveness Assessment (CEA), and other HTA-related elements. Additional categories covered health technology types, regulatory frameworks, decision-making, pricing, and post-launch activities.

3. Results

The taxonomy tool comprises 374 terms, each categorised according to the established taxonomy. Table 1 lists these terms alongside their definitions, classifications, and sources of definitions. Terms are presented in boldface text. Definitions may reference other terms included in the tool using 'See' for direct connections (i.e., terms used in the definition) or 'See also' for related terms. To enhance accessibility, [a web-based version](#) of this tool has been developed. This web-based version, optimised for use on computers and mobile devices, features a search-as-you-type function and custom filters aligned with taxonomy categories to enhance navigation and usability (See Figure 1).

The tool will be updated annually throughout the project. Future versions will include identified emerging terms and additional terms suggested by the users. Any changes the users propose will be discussed until a consensus is reached.

SUSTAIN-HTA Taxonomy tool

Figure 1. A screenshot of the web-based version of the Taxonomy tool

4. Disclaimer

The terms and definitions presented in this tool have been chosen specifically for the context of the SUSTAIN-HTA project. They are not intended to be exhaustive or definitive, nor are they purposefully exclusive of other perspectives. Instead, these terms and definitions have been selected to best serve the objectives of the project and its activities. The definitions draw on sources selectively

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curated for their relevance to the project's scope rather than based on a comprehensive review of all available literature. Users should exercise caution when using this tool in different contexts.

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Table 1. Terms, Definitions, and Classifications in the Taxonomy Tool

Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Absolute risk	<p>The probability of an individual experiencing a particular health-related event over a specified time period.</p> <p>Note 1: Absolute risk is calculated by dividing the number of people experiencing the event by the total number who could potentially experience the event.</p> <p>Note 2: The same absolute risk can be expressed in different ways; for example, you can say you have a 1 in 10 risk of developing a certain disease in your life, and this can also be said to be a 10% risk or a 0.1 risk.</p>	REA	[1]
Absolute risk reduction	<p>The value of the difference between the probability that an event will occur in the group exposed to a given factor and the probability that this event will occur in the group not exposed to this factor.</p> <p>Note: For example, if the results of a trial were that the probability of death was 25% in the control group and 10% in the experimental group, the absolute risk reduction would be $0.25 - 0.10 = 0.15$.</p> <p>Synonym: Risk difference</p> <p>See also “Number needed to treat”, “Odds ratio”, and “Relative risk reduction”.</p>	REA	[1]
Accuracy	<p>1) In the context of a study, the quality of a measurement (e.g. the mean estimate of a treatment effect) that is correct or that reflects the actual effectiveness of the treatment.</p> <p>Note: Not to be confused with preciseness: an estimate can be accurate, yet not be precise if it is based on an unbiased method that shows great random variations (severity of the disease, coexisting conditions).</p> <p>2) In the context of a diagnostic test, the proportion in which the results correspond to those of the chosen reference test, i.e. the sum of the true positives and the true negatives, divided by the size of the sample of the population studied.</p> <p>See also “Sensitivity” and “Specificity”.</p>	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Advanced therapy medicinal product (ATMP)	<p>A medicine for human use that is based on genes, cells or tissue engineering. ATMPs can be classified into three main types:</p> <p>Gene therapy medicines: these contain genes that lead to a therapeutic, prophylactic or diagnostic effect. They work by inserting ‘recombinant’ genes into the body, usually to treat a variety of diseases, including genetic disorders, cancer or long-term diseases. A recombinant gene is a stretch of DNA that is created in the laboratory, bringing together DNA from different sources.</p> <p>Somatic-cell therapy medicines: these contain cells or tissues that have been manipulated to change their biological characteristics or cells or tissues not intended to be used for the same essential functions in the body. They can be used to cure, diagnose or prevent diseases.</p> <p>Tissue-engineered medicines: these contain cells or tissues that have been modified so they can be used to repair, regenerate or replace human tissue; in addition, some ATMPs may contain one or more medical devices as an integral part of the medicine, which are referred to as combined ATMPs. An example of this is cells embedded in a biodegradable matrix or scaffold.</p> <p>See also “Gene therapy”.</p>	Health Technology	[2]
Affordability	The extent to which medicines and further health care products are available to the people who need them at a price they/their health system can pay.	Payer/Pricing; HTA decision-making; Other HTA elements	[3]
Aggregate study data	Summary data of the results of subjects of a trial, as opposed to individual patient data which represents the raw data of each subject.	REA	[4]
Analytic perspective	The viewpoint chosen for a given analysis, including a viewpoint of society, the government, the health care system or the payer.	CEA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Applicability	The degree to which evidence is considered relevant to a different population, setting, time or treatment variable. See also “External validity”.	REA; CEA	[1]
Appraisal	The political process of making a decision about a medicinal product and/or medical device, taking account of assessment information as well as values and other factors.	HTA decision-making	[5]
Assessment	A scientific process used to describe and analyse the properties of a health technology—its safety, efficacy, feasibility and indications for use, cost and cost-effectiveness, as well as social, economic and ethical consequences.	REA; CEA; Other HTA elements	[1]
Attrition bias	A bias associated with the dropping out or the differential exclusion of subjects from a study. Note: If subjects drop out of the study for some reason, their exclusion from the analysis could lead to an overestimate of the effectiveness of the intervention. The differential dropping out of subjects may be due to a selection bias in a comparative experimental study or cohort observation study.	REA	[1]
Authorisation under exceptional circumstances (EU)	A type of marketing authorisation granted to medicines granted by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) when the applicant is unable to provide comprehensive data on the efficacy and safety under normal conditions of use, because the condition to be treated is rare or because collection of full information is not possible or is unethical. Abbreviated as AEC.	Regulatory	[6]
Base case analysis	A base case analysis usually refers to the results obtained from running an economic model with the most likely or preferred set of assumptions and input values. Sensitivity analyses may then be used to explore how the results deviate from those of the base case analysis when input values and/or modelling assumptions are altered. ‘Reference case’ (analysis) may be used as an alternative to base case analysis, especially where analysts are directed to a standard set of modelling assumptions by an HTA organisation.	CEA	[7]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Basket trial	To study a single targeted therapy in the context of multiple diseases or disease subtypes. A Master Protocol designed to test a single investigational drug or drug combination in different populations defined by disease stage, histology, number of prior therapies, genetic or other biomarkers, or demographic characteristics.	REA	[8,9]
Bayesian analysis	A statistical method that explicitly includes a prior probability distribution based on a subjective opinion or objective evidence, such as the results of previous research. Note: Bayesian analysis uses Bayes' theorem to update the prior probability distribution in light of the results of a study in order to produce a posterior distribution. It can be used in a single study or in a meta-analysis. Statistical inference (point estimates, confidence intervals, etc.) is based on the posterior distribution. The posterior distribution can also be used as the prior distribution for the next study. This approach is controversial when it depends on opinions, which may vary. However, its use has become commonplace in economic evaluation, as it allows the creation of complex models with different evidence sources and the determination of uncertainty.	REA; CEA	[1]
Before-and-After study	A research design where a group of subjects is observed before and after an intervention or exposure to a given factor. Synonym: "pre-test/post-test study".	REA	[1]
Bias	A systematic error that may distort the results of a study because of weaknesses in its design, analysis, or reporting. Note: There are many different types of bias, including allocation bias, attrition bias, detection bias, outcome reporting bias, and selection bias. See also "Confounder".	REA; CEA	[1]
Big data	Data characterised by large increases in the amount of data, in the accumulation rate, and in the types of data present, requiring novel analytical approaches to manage these features.	REA; CEA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Bioethics	A field of inquiry comprising the analysis of ethical issues and moral dilemmas pertaining to the study, classification, and manipulation of biological life, especially human health.	Other HTA elements	[1]
Biomarker	A biomarker is a defined characteristic that is objectively measured as an indicator of normal biological processes, pathologic processes, or responses to an exposure or intervention, including therapeutic interventions. In a drug development context, biomarkers may be used for several different purposes, such as identifying patients for clinical trial enrolment, monitoring the safety of a therapy, or determining if a treatment is having the desired effect on the body.	REA	[10]
Biosimilar	A biosimilar is a biological medicine highly similar to another already approved biological medicine (the ‘reference medicine’) in terms of structure, biological activity and efficacy, safety and immunogenicity profile. A biosimilar is not regarded as a generic of a biological medicine. This is mostly because the natural variability and more complex manufacturing of biological medicines do not allow an exact replication of the molecular micro-heterogeneity.	Health Technology	[11]
Blinding	The concealment from study participants, investigators and/or assessors of the intervention being provided. Note: Blinding is undertaken to reduce the risk of bias. Synonym: Masking	REA	[1]
Budget impact analysis	An evaluation of the financial impact of the introduction of a technology or service on the capital and operating budgets of a government or agency.	Other HTA elements	[1]
Burden of disease	The burden of disease is a measurement of the gap between a population’s current health and the optimal state where all people attain full life expectancy without suffering major ill-health. Burden of disease analysis enables decision-makers to identify the most serious health problems facing a population. Loss of health in populations is measured in Disability-adjusted life years (DALYs), which is the sum of years of life lost due to premature death and years lived with disability.	CEA	[3]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	See “Disability-adjusted life year (DALY)”.		
Carer	<p>1) A duly trained and paid person who provides a person with a disease or disability with care.</p> <p>2) A person (often a family member or friend), paid or unpaid, who regularly provides a person with a disease or disability with any form of care.</p> <p>Synonym: Caregiver</p>	Other HTA elements	[1]
Case	In epidemiology, a person with the disease or characteristic of interest in a clinical trial.	REA	[1]
Case report	A detailed report of the symptoms, signs, diagnosis, treatment, and follow-up of an individual patient. Case reports usually also contain some demographic information about the patient (for example, age, gender, ethnic origin).	REA	[12]
Case series	<p>A group or series of case reports involving patients who were given similar treatment.</p> <p>See “Case report”.</p>	REA	[12]
Case-control study	<p>An observational study that compares the history of exposure to a particular risk factor or intervention for two groups of people from the same population, where one group has a specified outcome or disease (cases) and the other group does not (controls).</p> <p>Note 1: Investigators retrospectively compare the histories (in terms of past exposure history to particular risk factors) of the cases and controls to determine whether there is an association between the outcome and the cause being studied.</p> <p>Note 2: The groups should be similar in terms of certain characteristics, such as age and gender.</p> <p>Note 3: The term “Case-control study” is often incorrectly considered a synonym of retrospective study.</p>	REA	[1]
Causality	An association between a cause and an effect it produces.	REA; CEA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	<p>Note: A cause is termed “necessary” when it must always precede an effect. This effect need not be the sole result of the one cause. A cause is termed “sufficient” when it inevitably initiates or produces an effect. Any given cause may be necessary, sufficient, neither, or both.</p>		
Centralised procedure (EU)	<p>The European Union-wide procedure for the authorisation of medicines, where there is a single application, a single evaluation and a single authorisation throughout the European Union. The centralised procedure is compulsory for:</p> <p>Human medicines containing a new active substance to treat: Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) or Acquired immune deficiency syndrome (AIDS); Cancer; Diabetes; neurodegenerative diseases; auto-immune and other immune dysfunctions; viral diseases.</p> <p>Medicines derived from biotechnology processes, such as genetic engineering.</p> <p>Advanced-therapy medicines, such as gene-therapy, somatic cell-therapy or tissue-engineered medicines.</p> <p>Orphan medicines (medicines for rare diseases).</p> <p>Veterinary medicines for use as growth or yield enhancers.</p> <p>See also “Orphan medicinal product”, “Advanced therapy medicinal product (ATMP)”, and “Gene-therapy medicine”.</p>	Regulatory	[13]
Centrally authorised product (EU)	<p>A medicine with a single marketing authorisation issued by the European Commission and valid across the European Union.</p> <p>See also “Marketing authorisation” and “EMA Marketing authorisation”.</p>	Regulatory	[11]
Clinical endpoint	<p>A characteristic or variable that reflects how a patient feels, functions, or survives. Clinical endpoints are distinct measurements or analyses of disease characteristics reflecting the effect of a therapeutic intervention in a clinical trial or study.</p>	REA	[14]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Clinical guideline	<p>A guideline developed using a systematic method to help practitioners and patients make decisions about appropriate health care.</p> <p>Note: The development of clinical guidelines may use technology assessment methods or be based on technology assessment reports.</p> <p>Synonym: Clinical practice guideline</p>	REA; CEA; HTA-decision making	[1]
Clinical outcome	<p>An outcome of major importance for the patient, determined on the basis of the health problem being studied (e.g. the frequency of healing of osteoporotic fractures or gastric ulcers, and their relapse rates).</p> <p>Note: The clinical outcome differs from the health outcome in that the former has to do with the effect on the disease, while the latter has to do with the effect on health (public health, for example).</p>	REA	[1]
Clinical significance	<p>A difference in effect size that the experts consider significant for clinical or strategic decisions, regardless of statistical significance.</p> <p>Note: In a trial with a large number of subjects, a small difference between the treatment group and the control group may be statistically significant but clinically unimportant. In a trial with a small number of subjects, an important clinical difference may be observed that is not statistically significant. A larger trial may be needed to confirm that the difference is statistically significant.</p>	REA	[1]
Clinical study	<p>Any investigation in relation to humans intended:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) to discover or verify the clinical, pharmacological or other pharmacodynamic effects of one or more medicinal products; 2) to identify any adverse reactions to one or more medicinal products; or 3) to study the absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion of one or more medicinal products, with the objective of ascertaining the safety and/or efficacy of those medicinal products. 	REA	[15]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Clinical trial	<p>A clinical study which fulfils any of the following conditions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) the assignment of the subject to a particular therapeutic strategy is decided in advance and does not fall within the normal clinical practice of the Member State concerned; 2) the decision to prescribe the investigational medicinal products is taken together with the decision to include the subject in the clinical study; or 3) diagnostic or monitoring procedures in addition to normal clinical practice are applied to the subjects. 	REA	[15]
Co-payment	<p>Insured patient's contribution towards the cost of a medical service covered by the insurer. It can be expressed as a percentage of the total cost of the service or as a fixed amount. Co-payment is a form of out-of-pocket payment. Co-payments might be designed in different formats. With regard to co-payments applied to medicines, commonly applied variants in European countries are prescription fees, percentage reimbursement/co-payment rates, and, to a lesser extent, deductibles.</p> <p>See also "Out-of-pocket payments".</p>	CEA; Other HTA elements; HTA-decision making	[3]
Cohort models	<p>A cohort model is frequently used in economic evaluation to represent the experience of a simulated cohort of patients who receive (or do not receive) a new therapy. The experience of each individual cohort member is not considered in detail. Decision trees and Markov processes are used to estimate the proportion of the cohort who experience health events or health states over time. Events and their associated costs, as well as the costs and utilities associated with health states, can be multiplied by the relevant proportion of the cohort and aggregated to summarise the experience of the cohort.</p>	CEA	[7]
Cohort study	<p>An observational study in which the parameters of a group of subjects exposed to a given factor are compared with those of a similar group of subjects not exposed to the factor.</p> <p>Note 1: To make the groups comparable, the investigators may match subjects exposed to a given factor with subjects not exposed to the factor on the basis of common characteristics (e.g. age, gender and disease severity) or may make the necessary</p>	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	<p>statistical adjustments to obtain, in the matched subjects, characteristics that are as similar as possible.</p> <p>Other definition:</p> <p>An observational study in which the investigators select and monitor a group (cohort) of subjects exposed and non-exposed to a given factor to verify the effects of the exposure to the factor on the health of the cohort's members.</p> <p>Note 2: This type of study is usually prospective, but may also be retrospective when the data have already been gathered. What is important is the starting point: identify the subjects exposed and not exposed to a given factor and then determine the health effects of the exposure.</p>		
Committee for Advanced Therapies (EU)	<p>The Committee for Advanced Therapies is the European Medicines Agency's committee responsible for assessing the quality, safety and efficacy of advanced therapy medicinal products (ATMPs) and following scientific developments in the field.</p> <p>Abbreviated as CAT.</p> <p>See "Advanced therapy medicinal product (ATMP)".</p>	Regulatory	[11]
Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use (EU)	<p>The Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use is the European Medicines Agency's (EMA) committee responsible for human medicines. It plays a vital role in the authorisation of medicines in the European Union. Abbreviated as CHMP.</p>	Regulatory	[16]
Committee for Orphan Medicinal Products (EU)	<p>The Committee for Orphan Medicinal Products is the European Medicines Agency's committee responsible for reviewing applications for orphan designation for medicines that are intended for the diagnosis, prevention or treatment of rare diseases.</p> <p>Abbreviated as COMP.</p> <p>See "Orphan medicinal product".</p>	Regulatory	[11]
Comorbidity	The presence of diseases coexisting with the disease being studied.	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	Alternative spelling: Co-morbidity		
Companion Diagnostic	A diagnostic test that provides information that is essential for the safe and effective use of a corresponding medicinal product. The test helps a healthcare professional determine whether a particular therapeutic product’s benefits to patients will outweigh any potential serious side effects or risks.	Health Technology	[17]
Comparative effectiveness research	The conduct and/or synthesis of research comparing different benefits and harms of alternative interventions and strategies to prevent, diagnose, treat, and monitor health conditions in routine clinical practice (i.e., the real world setting). Comparative effectiveness research includes both primary data collection and secondary analyses (such as systematic literature reviews, meta-analyses and economic evaluations).	REA; CEA	[17]
Comparator	In clinical research, a technology or intervention that serves as a reference in comparative studies. In health economics, an option with which the technology or intervention evaluated is compared.	REA; CEA	[1]
Compliance	<p>1) In research, a measure of the extent to which the subjects undergo an assigned intervention.</p> <p>Note 1: It may be the extent to which the subjects comply with the drug therapy, undergo the prescribed medical or surgical procedure, do the prescribed exercise regimen, abstain from smoking, etc.</p> <p>2) For investigators, the fact of following a research protocol.</p> <p>3) In a clinical setting, for subjects who are supposed to undergo a treatment or who are registered in a program, the fact of complying with the requirements of that treatment or program.</p> <p>Note 2: Since this word has these three meanings, to avoid any confusion, it might be better to refer to “compliance with the research protocol” when what is meant is the investigator’s compliance.</p>	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Conditional marketing authorisation (EU)	The approval granted by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) for a medicine that addresses unmet medical needs of patients on the basis of less comprehensive data than normally required. The available data must indicate that the medicine’s benefits outweigh its risks, and the applicant should be in a position to provide the comprehensive clinical data in the future. Abbreviated as CMA.	Regulatory	[11]
Conditional treatment continuation	Continuation of coverage for individual patients is conditioned upon meeting short-term treatment goals. See also “Managed entry”.	Post-launch	[3]
Confidence interval (CI)	A range of values below and above the point estimate that has a given probability of including the true value of a given parameter, such as a treatment effect. Note: The confidence interval is the area of uncertainty for the estimating of a parameter. The use of this interval reflects the fact that a study provides one estimate of a parameter, out of the many estimates that would be possible if the study were repeated several times. If an X% CI is constructed for each repetition, X% of the intervals will contain the true value of the parameter. Investigators typically use confidence intervals of 90%, 95% or 99%. Thus, a 95% confidence interval indicates that there is a 95% probability that the confidence interval calculated from a particular study includes the true value of the parameter. If the interval includes a null value (a difference in means of 0, an odds ratio or a relative risk of 1, or a correlation coefficient of 0, for example), the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. A narrow confidence interval around a point estimate indicates a more precise estimate than a wide confidence interval.	REA; CEA	[1]
Confidence profile method	A meta-analysis based on Bayesian statistics for combining results of multiple studies that have different research designs, such as randomised controlled trials and observational studies, by adjusting the results of each individual study for its methodological biases before combining the results into a probability distribution for the parameter(s) of interest. See “Meta-analysis”.	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Confounder	<p>A factor that distorts the apparent effect of an intervention on the outcome of interest, or that distorts the apparent association between the exposure and the outcome.</p> <p>Example: If people in the experimental group of a controlled trial are younger than those in the control group, it will be difficult to decide whether a lower risk of death in one group is due to the intervention or to the difference in ages. Age is then said to be a confounder.</p> <p>Note: The identification of confounders requires expert or substantive knowledge about the causal network of which the intervention (or exposure) and the outcome are part (e.g. pathophysiological and clinical knowledge). Attempts to select confounders solely on the basis of observed statistical associations may lead to bias.</p> <p>Synonyms: “Confounding variable” and “Confounding factor”.</p> <p>See also “Confounding bias”.</p>	REA; CEA	[1]
Confounding bias	<p>A systematic error that occurs when the estimate of a measure of association between exposure (e.g. healthcare intervention) and outcome (e.g. health status) is distorted by the effect of one or several extraneous variables (confounding factor(s)) that are independently related to the exposure and/or outcome.</p>	REA; CEA	[17]
Conjoint analysis	<p>Conjoint analysis is the analytical technique used in discrete choice experiments, which is used in healthcare to evaluate preferences from participants (patients, payers, commissioners) for different attributes of an intervention, without directly asking them to state their preferred options.</p>	Other HTA elements	[7]
Consensus development	<p>A process whereby a group of experts examines an issue and, through a vote or some other means, reaches an agreement on the solution to be chosen.</p> <p>Note: This process may be structured or unstructured and may employ a method such as the nominal group technique or the Delphi technique.</p> <p>See “Delphi technique”.</p>	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Consensus report	The recommendations or practice guidelines produced through expert consensus.	REA	[1]
Context bias	<p>A measurement bias due to the influence of the study’s context on the interpretation of the study’s results.</p> <p>Note: For example, when tests are done in groups with a high prevalence of a disease, readers are more likely to interpret the results as anomalies. A contextual factor may also be a prognostic factor in some cases, and if that happens, it may lead to a confusion bias. Also, evaluation of the effectiveness of support programs for antiretroviral treatment compliance may lead to questionable results if social determinants of health, such as access to drinking water in sub-Saharan Africa or the poverty of homeless persons in Canada, have not been taken into account.</p>	REA	[1]
Contingent valuation	<p>A method for determining the monetary value of an option or clinical outcome by means of surveys in which people are presented with situations and asked what the maximum price is that they would be willing to pay for this option or clinical outcome.</p> <p>See also “Willingness-to-pay (WTP)”.</p>	CEA	[1]
Control	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. In clinical trials comparing two or more interventions, a subject in the comparison group who is offered a placebo, receives no treatment or receives standard care. 2. In case-control studies, a person in the comparison group who is without the disease or clinical state of interest. 3. Statistical control in statistics control, a procedure to adjust the results to take into account extraneous factors that could distort them. 4. Infection control in public health, a programme aimed at reducing the extent or the consequences of an infectious disease. 	REA	[1]
Control group	A group of persons that serves as the basis of comparison for assessing the effects of the intervention applied to the subjects in the treatment group.	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	<p>Note: depending on the circumstances of the trial, a control group may receive no treatment, the usual or standard treatment, or a placebo. To make the comparison valid, the composition of the control group must resemble that of the treatment group as closely as possible.</p> <p>See also “Randomisation” and “Historical control”.</p>		
Controlled clinical trial (CCT)	<p>A trial comparing at least one intervention with a control, where eligible participants are allocated to an intervention or control group, with the intention of creating groups with similar baseline characteristics, prior to exposure to the intervention or control.</p> <p>Note: Not all controlled clinical trials are randomised.</p> <p>See also “Randomised controlled trial” and “Non-randomised controlled trial”.</p>	REA	[1]
Coordination Group on Health Technology Assessment (HTACG)	<p>The Regulation on health technology assessment (HTAR) established the Coordination Group on Health Technology Assessment (HTACG) composed of Member States’ representatives, mainly from HTA authorities and bodies. The HTACG consists of four subgroups: the subgroup for joint clinical assessments, the subgroup for joint scientific consultations, the subgroup for identifying emerging health technologies, and the subgroup for developing methodological and procedural guidance.</p>	Regulatory	[18]
Correlation coefficient	<p>A correlation coefficient is a number between -1 and +1 that expresses the strength of the linear association between two numerical variables.</p> <p>Note 1: In a sample, the estimate is noted as <i>r</i>. A correlation coefficient of 0 indicates that there is no linear relationship between the two variables. A correlation coefficient of +1 indicates that there is a perfect positive linear relationship, and a correlation coefficient of -1 indicates that there is a perfect negative linear relationship.</p> <p>Note 2: It cannot be concluded from the correlation that there is a cause-and-effect relationship.</p>	REA; CEA	[1]
Cost	<p>The product of the quantity of a resource and the unit price of that resource.</p>	CEA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Cost of lost time	The cost of lost hours of work and decreased productivity due to disease, disability or death. Note: The value of the time is generally calculated on the basis of the average earnings.	CEA	[1]
Cost per QALY	A measure used in cost-utility analysis to compare programmes, interventions or treatments, expressed as a monetary cost per unit of outcome (effectiveness), adjusted on the basis of quality of life. See “Quality-adjusted life year (QALY)”.	CEA	[1]
Cost-benefit analysis (CBA)	An economic evaluation consisting of comparing various options, in which costs and outcomes are quantified in common monetary units.	CEA	[1]
Cost-consequence analysis	An economic evaluation consisting of comparing various options, in which the cost components and the various outcomes of a disease or intervention are calculated and presented separately.	CEA	[1]
Cost-effectiveness	The incremental monetary value of an intervention to its corresponding incremental effect on relevant health outcomes measures based upon an economic evaluation using an appropriate health economic model. The purpose of calculating cost-effectiveness is to structure evidence on clinical and economic outcomes in a form that can help to inform decisions about clinical practices and healthcare resource allocations. See also “Health economic model”.	CEA	[17]
Cost-effectiveness acceptability curve (CEAC)	A curve illustrating the probability that a given option is efficient on the basis of the value assigned to an additional quality-adjusted life year (QALY). See “Quality-adjusted life year (QALY)”.	CEA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA)	An economic evaluation consisting of comparing various options, in which costs are measured in monetary units, then aggregated, and outcomes are expressed in natural (non-monetary) units.	CEA	[1]
Cost-effectiveness threshold	The cost-effectiveness threshold is the maximum amount a decision-maker is willing to pay for a unit of health outcome. If the cost-effectiveness (ICER) of a new therapy (compared with a relevant alternative) is estimated to be below the threshold, then (other things being equal) it is likely that the decision-maker will recommend the new therapy. However, for values near the threshold, the level of uncertainty may become important. Thresholds are often established by analysis of previous (reimbursement) decisions: they are not themselves outputs of cost-effectiveness analyses, but guides (or rules) to interpretation of these outputs for decision-making, and they are specific to each unit of health outcome used. They are closely related to the economic concept of ‘opportunity cost’, in which the value of an intervention is considered to be the value of what is foregone in order to implement the intervention. The threshold value stands for the health outcome that could have been achieved if the resource required to implement the intervention of interest had been used elsewhere. Although some countries (e.g. NICE for England and Wales) make the thresholds that they use explicit, in other countries, the thresholds may not be explicit, and they may vary by healthcare sector or disease area. See “Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)” and “Opportunity cost”.	CEA	[7]
Cost-minimisation analysis (CMA)	An economic evaluation consisting of comparing the costs of various options presumed to produce equivalent outcomes and determining the least costly of those options. Alternate spelling: Cost-minimization analysis	CEA	[1]
Cost-of-illness analysis	An evaluation of the overall economic impact of a given disease or health problem on society. Note: The sum, expressed in monetary units, includes treatment costs but not treatment benefits or outcomes.	CEA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Cost-utility analysis (CUA)	<p>An economic evaluation consisting of comparing various options, in which costs are measured in monetary units and outcomes are measured in utility units, usually in terms of utility to the patient (using quality-adjusted life years, for example).</p> <p>Note: This is a form of cost-effectiveness analysis in which the effectiveness of an option is adjusted on the basis of quality of life.</p> <p>See “Cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA)” and “Quality-adjusted life year (QALY)”.</p>	CEA	[1]
Covariate	<p>A variable that exhibits covariation with a measured outcome or dependent variable. It is often included in an analysis so that its effect may be taken into account when interpreting the effects of the independent variables of interest.</p>	REA; CEA	[19]
Coverage with evidence development	<p>Early funding of a health technology conditional on gathering additional evidence to address the sources of uncertainty.</p> <p>Note: The uncertainty usually relates to a specific aspect of the effectiveness or cost-effectiveness.</p> <p>Synonyms: “Access with evidence development” and “Managed access”.</p>	HTA decision-making	[1]
Credible interval	<p>A range of values around the central estimate of a parameter, constructed using Bayesian methods.</p> <p>Note: The credible interval is the Bayesian equivalent of a confidence interval, but the interpretation of it is slightly different: the probability that a parameter is in an x% credible interval is x/100. For example, a 95% credible interval (0.82-1.36) for an odds ratio for mortality means that there is a 0.95 probability that the odds ratio in the population is between 0.82 and 1.36.</p>	REA; CEA	[1]
Critical appraisal	<p>The process of assessing and interpreting scientific research results by systematically analysing their validity, clinical and statistical significance, and clinical relevance.</p>	HTA decision-making	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Cross-sectional study	<p>An observational study in which the investigators choose a group of subjects in a given population and measure the simultaneous presence or absence of the risk factor and the outcome of interest.</p> <p>Note: The selection of the group of subjects is sometimes done through random sampling.</p> <p>Synonym: “Prevalence study”</p> <p>Antonym: “Longitudinal study”</p>	REA; CEA	[1]
Crossover trial	<p>A trial in which participants receive, in sequence, the experimental intervention, then, after a specified time, the control intervention, or vice versa.</p> <p>Note 1: In this type of trial, each participant serves as their own control, and randomisation may be used to determine the order (or sequence) in which the participant receives the experimental and control interventions.</p> <p>Note 2: Washout periods are usually included between the experimental and control phases of the trial to ensure that the effects of the first intervention do not carry over into the second phase of the trial.</p> <p>Synonyms: “Crossover study” and “Crossover design”.</p>	REA	[1]
Cumulative meta-analysis	<p>A meta-analysis presenting the gradual accumulation of the results of studies as the studies are added.</p> <p>Note: In a cumulative meta-analysis graph, each horizontal line represents the integration of the preceding studies, rather than the results of a single study. The studies are integrated one at a time and in a specified order (e.g. according to the date of publication or quality).</p> <p>See “Meta-analysis”.</p>	REA	[1]
Decision analysis	<p>A quantitative approach to facilitate decision-making under conditions of uncertainty that consists of modelling the pathways and outcomes for each possible option to determine which is optimal.</p>	CEA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	Note: This approach is based on the available estimates (from scientific literature or experts) of the probabilities that certain events and outcomes will occur and on the value of the outcomes that would result from each strategy.		
Decision tree	A graphical representation of the possible options and outcomes, used in decision analysis. See “Decision analysis”.	CEA	[1]
Delphi technique	An iterative group judgment technique in which a central source forwards surveys or questionnaires to isolated, anonymous (to each other) participants whose responses are collated/summarised and recirculated to the participants in multiple rounds for further modification/critique, producing a final group response (sometimes statistical).	REA	[20]
Dersimonian and Laird method	A noniterative, random-effects estimator of the between-study variance parameter that does not make any assumptions about the distribution of random effects. This method was introduced by Dersimonian and Laird (1986). Historically, random-effects meta-analysis has been based solely on this method. See “Random-effects model”.	REA	[21]
Deterministic sensitivity analysis (DSA)	Deterministic sensitivity analysis (DSA) is a method that can be used to investigate the sensitivity of the results from a model-based analysis to variations in a specific input parameter or set of parameters. One or more parameters are manually changed (usually across a pre-specified range), and the results are analysed to determine to what extent the change has an impact on the output values. The range of variation of each parameter is usually pre-specified, and where appropriate, it corresponds to the uncertainty in that parameter reported in source studies (for example, 95% confidence interval for efficacy from a source trial or meta-analysis). In univariate sensitivity analysis, one parameter is varied at a time, whilst in multivariate sensitivity analysis, more than one parameter is varied simultaneously. The results of deterministic sensitivity analysis are usually expressed as line graphs or bar charts. A ‘tornado chart’ refers to a summary (stack) of bar graphs representing univariate sensitivity analyses for a wide range of input values,	CEA	[7]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	ordered according to the extent (spread) of variation of the resulting model output value (with the widest variation on top). It is usually not possible to vary more than 4 to 5 parameters at the same time in this form of analysis: probabilistic sensitivity analysis is required to assess the impact of simultaneous variation of many input parameters. Univariate sensitivity analyses should be viewed with caution where input parameters are highly correlated (i.e. where parameters correlated to the parameter of interest are not varied together with the latter), such as sensitivity and specificity of diagnostic tests or utility of pre- and post-progression health states.		
Diagnosis related groups	A classification system of hospital cases used to pay hospital services, regardless of the cost to the hospital to provide services. The system is based not on the severity of the disease but on the amount of resources consumed. It categorises illness by diagnosis and treatment. A specific software ('grouper') groups patients into 'homogeneous groups' on the basis of diagnosis at discharge (coded by the international classification of diseases) and modified by the presence of a surgical procedure, patient age, presence or absence of significant comorbidities or complications, and other relevant criteria.	CEA	[3]
Differential pricing	Differential pricing is the strategy of selling the same product to different customers at different prices. In the case of (reimbursable) medicine, prices would vary among the countries according to their ability to pay. It was not introduced in the European countries due to the widespread practice of external price reference and the existence of parallel trade.	Payer/Pricing	[3]
Digital health	The application of digital technologies in healthcare. Note 1: Examples of eHealth technologies include mobile health technologies, electronic health records and telemedicine. Note 2: Digital health encompasses electronic health (eHealth), which in turn encompasses mobile health (mHealth). See "Electronic health record/electronic medical record (EHR/EMR)" and "Mobile health".	Health Technology	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Direct cost	All the fixed or variable costs of the resources (goods, services, etc.) monopolised in implementing an intervention and managing its consequences.	CEA	[1]
Direct medical cost	All the fixed or variable costs directly related to the delivery of health care and health services. Note: For example, physicians' compensation, hospital fees and drugs.	CEA	[1]
Direct non-medical cost	All non-medical expenses associated with the delivery of health care and health services. Note: For example, childcare expenses and expenses connected with travel to receive care.	CEA	[1]
Direct treatment comparison	The comparison of the relative effect(s) of several interventions for a particular therapeutic indication in a trial setting. The basis for comparison can vary (e.g. clinical endpoints, adverse effect rates, or drug adherence rates), and the trial type may vary (e.g. randomised controlled clinical trial, pragmatic clinical trial or observational study). See also "Comparator" and "Comparative effectiveness research".	REA	[17]
Disability-adjusted life year (DALY)	A unit of health status where life expectancy according to age is adjusted by the loss of health and years of life due to disability from disease or injury. Note: This measurement is often used to assess the overall burden of disease (for a large population).	REA; CEA	[1]
Discount	A price reduction granted to specified purchasers under specific conditions prior to purchase.	Payer/Pricing	[3]
Discount rate	The interest rate used to determine the present value of future costs and benefits. Note: The discount rate (e.g. 3% or 5%) is usually based on government borrowing rates (on three-month treasury bills, for example) or market interest rates where the maturity is equivalent to the period in which the intervention or program is evaluated. See "Discounting".	CEA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Discounting	<p>A mathematical process used to bring future costs and benefits to their present value.</p> <p>Note: These adjustments imply that future costs and benefits have less value than the same costs and benefits in the present.</p>	CEA	[1]
Discrete choice experiment (DCE)	<p>Discrete choice experiments are a type of survey-based research design used to measure people's preferences for different hypothetical scenarios. Participants are asked to choose between different options, each with varying levels of attributes, and the goal is to estimate the relative importance of each attribute.</p>	CEA; Other HTA elements	[22]
Discrete event simulation (DES)	<p>Discrete event simulation (DES) is a computer-modelling technique used in the economic evaluation of health interventions in which individual patient experience is simulated over time, and events occurring to the patient and the consequences of such events are tracked and summarised. Unlike cohort Markov models, in DES, movements between patients' health states are usually driven by events that may occur at varying times (rather than during cycles of fixed length), and time-to-event distributions are required for each event. Life courses of events and health states are constructed for a succession of individual modelled patients, which may then be aggregated over time to produce the summary experience of a patient cohort. Event likelihoods are driven by individual patient characteristics, which are recorded at baseline and may be updated as the patient experience (events, new health states) accumulates. Events and health states can be associated with resource use/cost and utilities. DES is likely to be useful for modelling complex conditions with many possible types of events and health states (e.g. complications of diabetes) or situations where the patient's history may impact future events. The building up of individual patient histories in DES gives this method some attraction, especially to clinician reviewers. However, the modelling can become more complex than more straightforward techniques (e.g. cohort Markov) and deriving time-to-event input values and distributions can be challenging.</p> <p>See "Markov model" and "Cohort models".</p>	CEA	[7]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Disease model	<p>A disease model is a simplified mathematical representation of the course of a disease over time in a patient cohort. In health technology assessment, disease models are used to represent the progression of chronic diseases and the impact of risk factors of interest on disease incidence, progression and mortality. Often, a micro-simulation approach is used, but simpler models may use a cohort Markov design (Markov model). Model inputs generally come from epidemiological studies. Disease models may be used to assess the potential impact of new therapies through varying the rates of progression or the balance of risk factors. They may form the basis of economic models, where specific treatment options are compared, and treatment costs and utility values are included as inputs.</p> <p>See “Markov model” and “Cohort models”.</p>	CEA	[7]
Disinvestment	<p>The deliberate and systematic reduction of funding for a health technology of questionable or comparatively low value.</p> <p>Note: The funding is often government funding, i.e., subsidisation of the costs of health care.</p>	HTA decision-making	[1]
Disutility	<p>Disutility represents the decrement in utility (valued quality of life) due to a particular symptom or complication. Disutility values are often expressed as negative values to represent the impact of the symptom or disease. They may be derived by subtracting utility values for a health state which includes the component (symptom, complication) of interest from a health state that is identical except for the absence of that component. Disutilities may be combined (usually additively, although occasionally multiplicative combinations are used) to provide a combined value of their collective impact on a patient’s quality of life. However, as with utilities, this needs to be done with care as there are situations where disutility $(A+B) \neq (\text{disutility}(A) + \text{disutility}(B))$ when the individual and combined health states are valued independently.</p> <p>See “Utility”.</p>	CEA	[7]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Dominance	The superiority of an option that entails lower costs than another option and has benefits equal to or greater than the other option, or that entails costs equal to those of another option and has greater benefits than the other option.	CEA	[1]
EMA Marketing authorisation	The approval to market a medicine in one, several or all European Union member states. See also “Marketing authorisation”.	Regulatory	[14]
EQ-5D	The EuroQol Five Dimension (EQ-5D) is an example of a generic measurement of quality of life, which is used in many clinical trials and other prospective studies. The EQ-5D questionnaire consists of 5 questions relating to different domains of quality of life (mobility, self-care, usual activities, pain/discomfort, anxiety/depression), for each of which there are 3 levels of response (no problems, some problems or severe problems). More recently, questions with 5 levels of response have been introduced (called EQ-5D-5L). The instrument is quick and easy to use, extensively researched/validated and translated into many different languages. Most importantly, it is not disease-specific and therefore applicable to most disease areas (but less applicable in mental health and diseases causing specific disabilities such as blindness) and to comparisons of interventions across disease areas. The importance of EQ-5D is that, based on population surveys, utility scores are available for each of the possible responses. These can be combined with appropriate durations for each measurement to generate quality-adjusted life years for each study subject, which in turn can be used to drive cost-utility analyses of the intervention of interest. It is generally recommended that in clinical trials, EQ-5D is administered alongside a disease-specific quality-of-life instrument, which is more sensitive to specific aspects of the condition and the potential impact of therapy.	REA; CEA	[7]
EU-GDPR	The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is a regulation that unifies data privacy laws across the European Union (EU) and enhances the protection of personal data for EU residents. This unification introduces new rights for individuals and creates a set of clearer and stronger rules for businesses. The GDPR applies to all companies that handle the personal data of EU residents, including those based outside the EU, if they provide goods	Regulatory	Adapted from [23]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	or services to EU residents or monitor their behaviours. The GDPR was enacted on May 25, 2018.		
Early awareness and alert system	<p>A system that aims to identify, filter and prioritise new and emerging health technologies, or new uses of existing interventions; to assess or predict their impact on health, health services and/or society; and to disseminate information.</p> <p>Note 1: ‘Filter’ is a process to remove technologies that are not relevant to the early awareness and alert system from the list of technologies originating from the identification process.</p> <p>Note 2: ‘Prioritise’ is a process to determine the significance of, or order for dealing with, filtered technologies according to their relative importance to the aims of the early awareness and alert system.</p> <p>Synonyms: “Early warning system” and “Horizon scanning system”</p>	Scanning	[1]
Economic evaluation	<p>The comparative analysis of the costs and consequences of two or more possible options.</p> <p>Note: Depending on whether the consequences are expressed as monetary, physical or qualitative variables, the analysis may be a cost-benefit, cost-effectiveness or cost-utility analysis.</p> <p>See “Cost-benefit analysis (CBA)”, “Cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA)”, and “Cost-utility analysis (CUA)”.</p>	CEA	[1]
Effect size	<p>A dimensionless measure of the degree of presence of a phenomenon in the population of interest.</p> <p>Note 1: In the case of continuous variables, it is generally defined as the difference in means between the experimental and control groups, divided by the standard deviation of the control group or both groups. When different scales (pain assessment, for example) are used to measure an outcome, they become comparable.</p> <p>Note 2: This measure is used to determine the size of a sample.</p>	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Effectiveness	The benefit of using a technology, programme or intervention to address a specific problem under general or routine conditions, rather than under controlled conditions, for example, by a physician in a hospital or by a patient at home. Synonyms: “Clinical effectiveness”	REA	[1]
Effectiveness study	Effectiveness studies (also referred to as real-world studies) measure the effects associated with a health intervention when prescribed in routine clinical practice and usual prescription conditions. Observational/non-interventional studies, pragmatic studies and large simple trials are all types of effectiveness studies. Key defining criteria of effectiveness studies include, but are not limited to: multiple active comparators; broad eligibility criteria for trial subjects; clinically meaningful health outcomes; large trial population and longer duration (c.f. RCT’s). Randomisation does not preclude a study from being able to measure effectiveness.	REA	[4]
Efficacy	The benefit of using a technology, programme or intervention to treat a particular problem under ideal conditions—for example, in the context of research in a laboratory or a rigorous protocol for a randomised clinical trial.	REA	[1]
Efficacy study	Efficacy studies, often referred to as explanatory studies, measure the effect of a drug under highly controlled conditions (i.e. in the setting of randomised controlled clinical trials (RCTs). They serve to prove the causal relationship between an intervention and an outcome, thus answering the question, “Can it work?” in an ideal world.	REA	[4]
Efficacy-effectiveness gap	The observed discrepancy between the effects of a health intervention in routine clinical practice as compared with the effects demonstrated in randomised controlled clinical trials.	REA	[4]
Efficiency	The allocation of available healthcare resources that maximise health outcomes for society.	HTA decision-making	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	Note: Efficiency is the combined effect of allocative efficiency and technical efficiency.		
Efficient Frontier	A curve formed by the incremental cost-effectiveness or cost-utility ratios in a graphical representation of the non-dominated comparators. See “Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)” and “Dominance”.	CEA	[1]
Electronic health record/electronic medical record (EHR/EMR)	An electronic record of health-related information on an individual that can be created, gathered, managed, and consulted by authorised clinicians and other healthcare professionals. Patient/subject health-related information may include all of the key administrative clinical data relevant to that person’s care under a particular provider, including demographics, progress notes, problems, medications, vital signs, past medical history, immunisations, laboratory data and radiology reports. See “Electronic healthcare data”.	REA	[17]
Electronic healthcare data	Analytic data that is “an organised set of [healthcare] data or collection of files available by computer through electronic format which can be used for the conduct of [safety] studies”. It is derived from a raw electronic healthcare database. Electronic healthcare data may include administrative claims data and Electronic medical record (EMR) data. See also “Electronic health record/electronic medical record (EHR/EMR)”.	REA	[17]
Emerging health technology	A health technology that has not yet been adopted within the healthcare system. Note: Pharmaceuticals are in the phase II or III clinical trial, or pre-launch stage; medical devices are in the pre-marketing stage. See also “Health technology” and “New health technology”.	Health Technology	[1]
Endpoint	A measure or indicator chosen for determining an effect of an intervention.	REA	[20]
Environmental risk assessment	Analysis of the potential risk that the use of a medicine poses to the environment.	Other HTA elements	[11]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Epidemiology	The study of the distribution and determinants of health-related states or events in specified populations.	REA; CEA	[1]
Equipoise	<p>A state of genuine uncertainty as to which of two or more alternative health technologies should constitute the standard of care, considering benefits and harms.</p> <p>Note 1: Equipoise is widely viewed as necessary for a trial to be ethically justified, especially when participants are assigned to trial arms randomly. This view is underpinned by the idea that physician-researchers cannot waive their duty to act in the best interests of their patients.</p> <p>Note 2: As specified by the definition, equipoise usually refers to the state of uncertainty inhabited by the scientific and medical community, but it can also refer to the state of uncertainty inhabited by the researchers conducting a trial or by patients and the public.</p>	REA; CEA	[1]
Equity	<p>The fair allocation of resources or treatments among different individuals or groups, such that they each get what they are owed or what they are entitled to.</p> <p>Other definition:</p> <p>The use of resource allocation rules based on the distributive justice principle. However, the latter involves various concepts that define these rules more precisely (merit, social value, the greater good, equal opportunity, equal treatment, priority to the most disadvantaged, standard gamble, etc.).</p> <p>Note: Vertical equity means that the people in the greatest need of services receive the most services, and horizontal equity means that people who have similar needs receive similar services.</p>	Other HTA elements	[1]
Equivalence trial	<p>A trial with the primary objective of showing that the difference between the responses to two or more interventions is clinically insignificant.</p> <p>Note: This objective is usually achieved by demonstrating that the actual difference between the treatments is likely to fall within a pre-determined zone in which the outcomes are deemed clinically equivalent.</p>	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Estimate of effect	<p>In a study, the relationship between the outcome observed when an intervention is applied and the outcome observed in a control group.</p> <p>Note: This relationship may be expressed as a number needed to treat, odds ratio, risk difference, relative risk, standardised mean difference or weighted mean difference.</p> <p>See also “Treatment effect”.</p>	REA	[1]
Ethics	<p>A theory aimed at determining what is good, both for the individual and for society as a whole.</p> <p>Other definition: A critical reflection on the aims and foundations of human action (including expressed values) and a guiding of human conduct through questioning, discussion and the proposing of guidelines, rather than the imposing of rules.</p> <p>Note: From this perspective, ethics differ from morality, which is a system and codification of requirements (standards and rules) governing human conduct, requirements characterised by their universality and by a restraining effect. Nonetheless, ethics, morality and law are closely interdependent.</p>	Other HTA elements	[1]
EuroScan	<p>The European information network on new and changing health technology (https://www.euroscan.org/).</p> <p>A network of health technology assessment agencies that identify and assess new and emerging technologies.</p> <p>See “Emerging health technology”.</p>	Scanning	[1]
Event rate	<p>The proportion of the members of a group in whom an event is observed over a specified period of time.</p> <p>Note: If an event (e.g. a stroke) is observed in 32 subjects out of a group of 100 monitored over one year, the stroke rate is 0.32 a year.</p>	REA	[1]
Evidence table	<p>A summary table of selected characteristics of the studies of a particular intervention or health problem.</p>	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	Note: this type of table includes characteristics such as the methodological plan, the subjects and the outcomes.		
Exchangeability	In the context of quantitative evidence synthesis, exchangeability is the assumption that if patients from one treatment group were substituted into another, the same treatment effect is expected; it involves the components of similarity, homogeneity, and, in the case of indirect comparisons, consistency.	REA	[24]
Expected Value of Partially Perfect Information (EVPPI)	The expected value of partially perfect information is the price that a healthcare decision maker would (in theory) be willing to spend in order to gain perfect information for one or more factors (i.e. inputs to an economic model) which may influence which treatment alternative is preferred, based on the analysis of uncertainty in the relevant cost-effectiveness analysis. The EVPPI is calculated as the difference in the monetary value of health gain associated with a decision between therapy alternatives (and represented in an economic model) between when a choice is made on the basis of currently available information (i.e. uncertainty in the factor(s) of interest) and when the choice is made based on perfect information (no uncertainty in these factors). EVPPI is closely related to EVPI (and EVSI) and is primarily used to assess the value of collecting further information, especially when this may involve expensive trials, registries or other observational studies.	CEA	[7]
Expected Value of Perfect Information (EVPI)	The expected value of perfect information is the price that a healthcare decision-maker would be willing to pay to have perfect information regarding all factors that influence which treatment choice is preferred as the result of a cost-effectiveness analysis. This is the value (in money terms) of removing all uncertainty from such an analysis. EVPI is calculated as the difference in the monetary value of health gain associated with a decision between therapy alternatives between when the choice is made on the basis of currently available information (i.e. uncertainty in the factors of interest) and when the choice is made based on perfect information (no uncertainty in all factors).	CEA	[7]
External validity	The ability of a research design to provide findings that can be generalised to other populations, contexts and periods.	REA; CEA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	Synonyms: “Generalisability”. See also “Applicability”.		
Extrapolation	A calculation, for values of the variable lying outside the series of observed variables, the values of an empirically known function and, by extension, the resulting prediction, deduction, forecasting, transposition or projection.	CEA	[1]
Factorial design	A design that allows for evaluating the effects of multiple interventions and their interactions within a clinical trial. Note: most trials consider only one experimental intervention, comparing it with one or more options or a placebo. In a trial using a 2×2 factorial design, participants are allocated to one of four possible combinations. For example, in a randomised controlled trial of a nicotine replacement therapy and counselling, participants would be allocated to: nicotine replacement therapy alone, counselling alone, both, or neither. In this way, it is possible to test the independent effect of each intervention on smoking cessation and the combined effect of (interaction between) the two interventions.	REA	[1]
False negative error	In hypothesis testing, an error that occurs when it is incorrectly concluded that a null hypothesis is true. Note: For example, a type II error is made if no difference is detected between the outcomes in an experimental group and those in a control group when in fact such a difference exists. The probability of making this type of error is designated as beta (β). Synonym: “Type II error”	REA	[1]
False positive error	In hypothesis testing, an error that occurs when it is incorrectly concluded that a null hypothesis is false. Note: For example, a Type I error is made if a difference is detected between the outcomes in an experimental group and those in a control group when in fact such a difference does not exist. The probability of making this type of error is designed as alpha (α).	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	Synonym: “Type I error”		
Federated data network	<p>A federated data network uses a common platform to facilitate bi-directional data flow, data harmonisation (from diverse sources) and connectivity for research reuse; supported by a harmonisation fund and certified/qualified SME network. A federated data network retains local provenance and governance while facilitating remote connectivity with real world data (RWD) for research reuse.</p> <p>See also “Real world data (RWD)”.</p>	REA; CEA	[14]
Fixed-effect model	<p>In a meta-analysis, a statistical model that takes only within-study variability into account in the assessment of the degree of uncertainty (confidence interval) of the combined effect from the studies.</p> <p>Note: The fixed-effect model assumes that the units analysed are the units of interest and, consequently, that they make up the population of units. In such a model, variation between the estimates of effect from each study (heterogeneity) does not affect the confidence interval.</p> <p>See also “Random-effects model” and “Peto method”.</p> <p>Alternative spelling: Fixed effect model</p>	REA	[1]
Follow-up	<p>An observation, over a given period, of a person, group or population defined at the outset, certain characteristics of whom or of which are evaluated to identify the changes in their health status or in certain health-related variables.</p> <p>Note: If data on the effects on subjects of the intervention being studied are lost (because subjects have moved or have dropped out for some other reason), the study’s results may be influenced, especially if some types of subjects are systematically lost from the study for the same reasons. The investigators must report the number and type of subjects who could not be evaluated, in order that the possibility of bias may be taken into consideration.</p> <p>See also “Intention-to-treat (ITT) analysis”.</p>	REA; CEA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Forest plot	A Forest plot provides a graphic summary of the size of the overall effect of all the included studies from a meta-analysis within a systematic review. The weighted effect sizes and statistical heterogeneity are displayed as a plot with the summary effect size depicted as a diamond figure within the plot.	REA	[25]
Friction-cost method	A method of estimating the cost of the production loss resulting from the absence of an employee during the period needed by the organisation to replace the employee and return to the initial level of productivity.	CEA	[1]
Funnel plot	A scatter diagram in which each point represents a study, relating the estimate of effect and the sample size (or another indicator of the precision of the study). Note: In the absence of publication bias, the scatter diagram will form an inverted funnel. A hole in the lower left corner of the funnel indicates the presence of publication bias.	REA	[1]
GRADE	The GRADE approach is a system for rating the quality of a body of evidence in systematic reviews and other evidence syntheses, such as health technology assessments, and guidelines and grading recommendations in health care. GRADE offers a transparent and structured process for developing and presenting evidence summaries and for carrying out the steps involved in developing recommendations. It can be used to develop clinical practice guidelines (CPG) and other health care recommendations (e.g. in public health, health policy and systems and coverage decisions).	REA; CEA	[26]
Gene-therapy medicine	See “Advanced therapy medicinal product (ATMP)”.	Health Technology	[2]
Generalisability	Generalisability refers to whether the results of an HTA report can be extrapolated to other settings. Note: Generalisability and Transferability might be used with a similar but slightly different meaning. For example, ISPOR’s Good Research Practices Task Force wrote a guideline on the transferability of economic evaluations across jurisdictions and applied the following working definitions: “economic evaluations were generalizable if they applied, without	REA; CEA	[27,28]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	<p>adjustment, to other settings. On the other hand, data were transferable if they could be adapted to apply to other settings”.</p> <p>See also “External validity” and “Transferability”</p>		
Grey literature	<p>The documents published for a limited audience, outside the major distribution channels, and difficult to find in the usual databases, such as presentations at conferences, health technology assessments done by hospitals, and certain government documents.</p> <p>Note: There is a lack of unanimity on the definition of grey literature, as the boundaries of this literature continually shift and evolve as new technical means are developed.</p> <p>Alternative spelling: Gray literature</p>	REA; CEA	[1]
HTA report	<p>A report that includes a comprehensive systematic literature review, or a systematic review of high-level evidence, evaluating the safety and effectiveness of a technology, as well as an analysis of the cost-effectiveness of the technology.</p> <p>Note 1: The report always:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • describes the characteristics and current use of the technology; • critically appraises the quality of the evidence base; • provides information on costs and financial impact; and • discusses organisational considerations. <p>Note 2: The report may optionally address ethical, social and legal considerations arising from the use of the technology.</p> <p>Note 3: The cost-effectiveness of the technology may be addressed through economic modelling, when it is appropriate.</p> <p>See also “Health technology assessment” and “Rapid review”.</p>	REA; CEA; Other HTA elements	[1]

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Handsearching	The methodological searching, page by page (by hand) of the content of a journal, including articles, editorials, letters from readers, etc., to identify the relevant studies and complete the non-indexed searching in the databases. Note: Normally, one starts with the issues from the current year, and then works backwards until the yield becomes negligible or the first volume is reached.	REA; CEA	[1]
Health	A state of complete physical, social and mental well-being, and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. Health is a resource for everyday life, not the object of living. It is a positive concept emphasising social and personal resources as well as physical capabilities. It is recognised, however, that health has many dimensions (anatomical, physiological, and mental) and is largely culturally defined.	REA; CEA; Other HTA elements; HTA-decision making	[3]
Health Utilities Index (HUI®)	A generic and complete scoring system based on various users' preferences and designed to measure health status and quality of life and to produce utility scores.	REA; CEA	[1]
Health economic model	A logical mathematical framework demonstrating the quantitative relationship between a defined set of variables (e.g. cost, effectiveness, net benefit) based upon an explicit set of parameters and assumptions. The purpose of modelling is to structure evidence on clinical and economic outcomes in a form that can help to inform decisions about clinical practices and healthcare resource allocations.	CEA	[17]
Health economics	A scientific discipline that seeks to apply the principles and rules of economics in the healthcare field. Note: Health economics includes the evaluation of the health system and of health policies from an economic perspective, of the demand for and supply of health care, and of medical technologies and interventions; it also includes health system resources planning and organisation, consideration and evaluation of the determinants of health, and analysis of health system performance in terms of equity and allocative efficiency.	CEA	[1]
Health economics and	Health Economics and Outcomes Research (HEOR) is the most common label given to the function within pharmaceutical and life science companies with the responsibility for	REA; CEA	[7]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
outcomes research (HEOR)	generating evidence of the value of new interventions for reimbursement agencies and local health care payers. While ‘HE’ refers mostly to skills in economic evaluation ‘OR’ may refer to expertise in observational studies or in the development and use of new health outcomes measurements, especially patient-reported outcomes (PROs). HEOR staff will advise on the design of trials to best meet the needs of healthcare payers, as well as on other studies and analyses (meta-analyses, modelling, observational studies) that may be required. They will ensure that these studies are executed, often using external researchers, and will communicate the results internally and externally. If based in specific countries, they may be responsible for creating and delivering submissions to reimbursement agencies or local healthcare payers. HEOR staff work closely with specialists in Market Access.		
Health outcome	The result of an intervention (or the absence of an intervention) on the health or well-being of a subject or a population. Note 1: The intervention may be a clinical procedure, social intervention, health policy, public programme, etc. Note 2: The health outcome differs from the clinical outcome in that the former has to do with the effect on health (public health, for example), while the latter has to do with the effect on the disease.	REA; CEA	[1]
Health services research	An interdisciplinary field of inquiry that examines the impact of the organisation, financing and management of healthcare services on the delivery, quality, cost, accessibility and outcomes of such services.	REA; Other HTA elements	[1]
Health status	The level of health of a person, group or population, as assessed by the person himself/herself or through objective measures.	REA; CEA	[1]
Health technology	An intervention developed to prevent, diagnose or treat medical conditions; promote health; provide rehabilitation; or organise healthcare delivery.	Health Technology	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	<p>Note: The intervention can be a test, device, medicine, vaccine, procedure, program or system.</p>		
Health technology assessment	<p>A multidisciplinary process that uses explicit methods to determine the value of a health technology at different points in its lifecycle. The purpose is to inform decision-making in order to promote an equitable, efficient, and high-quality health system.</p> <p>Acronym: HTA</p> <p>Note 1: The process is formal, systematic and transparent, and it uses state-of-the-art methods to consider the best available evidence.</p> <p>Note 2: The dimensions of value for a health technology may be assessed by examining the intended and unintended consequences of using a health technology compared to existing alternatives. These dimensions often include clinical effectiveness, safety, costs and economic implications, ethical, social, cultural and legal issues, organisational and environmental aspects, as well as wider implications for the patient, relatives, caregivers, and the population. The overall value may vary depending on the perspective taken, the stakeholders involved, and the decision context.</p> <p>Note 3: HTA can be applied at different points in the lifecycle of a health technology, i.e., pre-market, during market approval, post-market, through to the disinvestment of a health technology.</p> <p>See “Health technology”.</p>	<p>REA; CEA; Other HTA elements; Regulatory; HTA decision-making</p>	[1]
Health technology assessment (HTA) body	<p>A public organisation that provides recommendations on medicines and other healthcare interventions that can be paid for or reimbursed. These organisations look at the relative effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of medicines that have been authorised.</p>	<p>HTA decision-making</p>	[11]
Health-related quality of life (HRQoL)	<p>The measures of the impact of an intervention on patients’ health status, extending beyond the traditional measures of mortality and morbidity to include dimensions such as</p>	<p>REA; CEA</p>	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	<p>physiology, function, social life, cognition, emotions, sleep and rest, energy and vitality, health perception and general life satisfaction.</p> <p>Note: Some of these elements are also called health status, functional status or quality-of-life measures.</p>		
Healthy-years equivalent (HYE)	The hypothetical number of years spent in perfect health which could be considered equivalent to the actual number of years spent in a defined imperfect state of health.	CEA	[1]
Heterogeneity	<p>In a systematic review, the variability of or differences in the selected studies.</p> <p>Note: A distinction is sometimes made between “statistical heterogeneity” (differences in the reported effects) and “methodological heterogeneity” (differences in study design with regard to the key characteristics of the subjects, interventions or outcome evaluation criteria). Statistical tests of heterogeneity are used to determine whether the observed variability in study results effect size is greater than the variability that can be expected to occur by chance. However, these tests have low statistical power.</p> <p>Antonym: “Homogeneity”</p>	REA; CEA	[1]
Hierarchy of evidence	<p>A ranking of study designs based primarily on their internal validity.</p> <p>Note 1: This method is used to determine the weight that should be given to a study.</p> <p>Note 2: Various hierarchies of evidence are used in health technology assessment.</p>	REA; CEA	[1]
Historical control	<p>A control group made up of persons who have been observed on an occasion previous to the present one involving observation of the group of interest.</p> <p>Note: The validity of comparisons with this type of control group is suspect because the historical group is likely to differ from the current group in its composition, diagnosis, disease severity, measurement of outcomes, or other important ways that could influence the research findings. It may be feasible to use historical controls in special instances where the outcomes of a standard treatment (or no treatment) are well-known and vary little for a given population.</p>	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Historical control study	A study in which the data for the control group are collected at a time period prior to that for the intervention group. Note: Historical control studies are prone to selection bias.	REA	[1]
Homogeneity	In a systematic review, the similarity of the studies selected. Note: studies are considered “statistically homogeneous” if their results vary no more than they might be expected to by chance. In a systematic review, “clinical homogeneity” means that the subjects, interventions and measuring instruments are similar or comparable. Antonym: “Heterogeneity”	REA	[1]
Horizon scanning	The systematic identification of health technologies that are new, emerging or becoming obsolete and that have the potential to affect health, health services and/or society. See also “Early awareness and alert system”.	Scanning	[1]
Hospitalisation rate	The number of hospital cases in a given population over an established period of time. Statistics on hospitalisation rate can be disaggregated by reasons for hospitalisation (according to major diagnostic categories or at lower level) and/or by age.	REA; CEA; Other HTA elements	[3]
Hypothesis	A supposition or assumption advanced as a basis for reasoning or argument, or as a guide to experimental investigation.	REA; CEA	[14]
Hypothesis testing	A method of statistical inference for evaluating the plausibility of the null hypothesis in the light of the observed data. Note: The null hypothesis is assumed to be true at the outset, but, if that assumption proves wrong when the observed data are examined, it is rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis (negative of the null hypothesis).	REA; CEA	[1]
Incidence	The number of new cases of a disease or condition in a population at risk over a given period, usually one year.	REA; CEA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Incremental cost	The difference between the cost of an option and the cost of another option with which it is compared.	CEA	[1]
Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)	The additional cost of the more expensive intervention compared with the less expensive intervention, divided by the difference between the effects of the interventions on the patients (the additional cost per QALY, for example).	CEA	[1]
Indirect cost	All costs attributed to the value of economic production lost due to disease, a disabling injury or premature death. Note: Not to be confused with indirect costs in accounting, where the term refers to overhead costs.	CEA	[1]
Indirect treatment comparisons (ITC)	The comparison of several (i.e., 2 or more) interventions for a particular therapeutic indication in the absence of a trial that directly compares the interventions in question. Indirect comparisons made via a shared a comparator treatment are referred to as anchored indirect comparisons, whereas those made without the use of a shared comparator are called unanchored indirect comparisons.	REA	[4,29]
Individual patient data (IPD)	Raw data for subjects included in a study as opposed to aggregate data (summary data for the comparison groups in each study).	REA; CEA	[17]
Informed consent	The legal and ethical obligation not to perform any significant medical procedure until a competent patient has been informed of the nature and risks of the procedure and the alternatives to it, as well as of the prognosis if the procedure is not done. Note: If the patient agrees to the procedure, he or she must do so freely and voluntarily.	Other HTA elements; Regulatory	[1]
Intention-to-treat (ITT) analysis	An analysis in which the effects observed in the subjects of a trial are evaluated according to the intervention to which they were randomised, whether or not they received it, or whether or not they complied with the study protocol.	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	<p>Note: This type of analysis is favoured because it maintains the equivalence of the randomised groups. Also, in the evaluation of the practical effectiveness of an intervention, it mirrors the non-compliance and the treatment changes likely to occur in practice.</p> <p>See also “Per protocol”.</p>		
Inter-rater reliability	<p>The degree of stability of a measurement when it is repeated under identical conditions by different raters.</p> <p>Note: Inter-rater reliability makes it possible to determine the degree to which the results obtained can be replicated. Lack of this reliability may arise from divergences between raters or instability of the attribute measured.</p> <p>See also “Intra-rater reliability”.</p>	REA	[1]
Interim analysis	<p>An analysis performed during a study to compare the experimental groups with regard to the effectiveness or safety of an intervention, when the situation requires.</p> <p>Note: Interim analyses must be planned in the protocol (their number, the time of their application, the criteria underlying them, etc.). They differ from the standard analysis, which is performed at the end of the follow-up period provided for in the study protocol. The number of subjects in a study must reflect the planned number of interim analyses.</p>	REA	[1]
Intermediate outcome	<p>An intermediate outcome is an outcome such as a measure of a function or of a symptom (e.g., disease free survival, angina frequency, exercise tolerance) but is not the ultimate outcome of the disease such as survival or the rate of irreversible morbid events (stroke, myocardial infarction).</p> <p>Note: An intermediate outcome is not a synonym for a surrogate outcome. An intermediate outcome can become a surrogate outcome if it is easier to measure than a clinical criterion, if there is a statistical relationship between the occurrence of the clinical outcome indicator and the intermediate outcome, or if there is a relationship allowing for the prediction of the effect of the factor studied on the clinical indicator based on the observed effect on the intermediate outcome.</p>	REA	[1, 30]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	See also “Surrogate outcome”		
Internal validity	<p>The ability of a research design to represent the true causal relationship between an intervention and an effect in the particular circumstances of the research.</p> <p>Note: If the internal organisation of a study leads to distortion in the estimation measurement, that measurement lacks internal validity. This is what happens when, for example, a person is weighed using a defective scale. As with a well-calibrated scale, an etiological study must be free of measurement-distorting internal defects. These defects may be encountered at three stages in the study: the subject selection, information-gathering and analysis stages.</p>	REA; CEA	[1]
International Horizon Scanning Initiative (IHSI)	The International Horizon Scanning Initiative (IHSI) is a collaboration of nine countries with the aim of fostering collaboration on Joint Horizon Scanning. IHSI provides comprehensive data that empowers political decision-makers and payer organisation negotiators to drive for better pricing in medicinal products. IHSI data enables healthcare systems to prepare for disruptive technologies through data insights that deliver the leverage required to confidently assess new products coming to market.	Scanning	[31]
International classification of diseases (ICD)	The WHO (World Health Organization) international standard diagnostic classification coding system used for all general epidemiological and many health management purposes. The purpose of the ICD is to permit the systematic recording, analysis, interpretation and comparison of mortality and morbidity data collected in different countries or areas and at different times.	REA	[3]
Interrupted time series	<p>A study of the therapeutic effect of a technology through comparison of the results of multiple measurements taken before and after the technology is used in a given group of subjects.</p> <p>Note: the value of this type of study can be strengthened by the addition of a control group in which the technology has not been tried and which is observed at the same points in time. Also, multiple time series can be studied by staggering the introduction of the technology.</p>	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Interventional study	See “Clinical trial”.	REA	[15]
Intra-rater reliability	<p>The degree of stability observed when a measurement is repeated under identical conditions by the same rater.</p> <p>Note: Intra-rater reliability makes it possible to determine the degree to which the results obtained by a measurement procedure can be replicated. Lack of intra-rater reliability may arise from divergences between measurement instruments or instability of the attribute measured.</p> <p>See also “Inter-rater reliability”.</p>	REA	[1]
Inverse variance method	A widely used and easy-to-implement method of pooling study results, which is very flexible and can be used to combine any type of effect measure provided that standard errors are available. A fixed effect meta-analysis using the generic inverse variance method calculates a weighted average of study effect estimates by summing individual effect estimates and weighting these by the reciprocal of their squared standard errors.	REA	[32]
Joint Clinical Assessment (EU)	The EU Joint Clinical Assessment (JCA) is a collaborative effort among EU member states to evaluate the clinical evidence of new treatments. The aim of the JCA is to enhance efficiency and consistency in decision-making regarding new health technologies across Europe by replacing individual country clinical assessments with a unified, transparent process. Abbreviated as (JCA).	HTA decision-making	[33]
Joint procurement	The procurement of certain products or services is done by a single purchasing body for several healthcare providers (e.g. hospitals, regions, countries).	Payer/Pricing	[3]
Joint scientific consultation (JSC)	Joint Scientific Consultation (JSC) is a voluntary procedure for health technology developers to gain input jointly from EU Health Technology Assessment (HTA) bodies on clinical development and evidence requirements. It is part of the new EU Regulation on Health Technology Assessment (HTAR), effective from 12 January 2025. The purpose of JSC is to exchange information on development plans and facilitate evidence generation	HTA decision-making	[34]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	that meets the likely evidence requirements of a subsequent Joint Clinical Assessment (JCA) for the product. JSC may also include parallel consultations with the European Medicines Agency (EMA) for medicines or expert panels for medical devices. #Check again when implementing act is published in 6 months		
Kappa statistic	A measure of the degree of agreement between two measures of the same categorical variable over and above the agreement that is due to chance alone. Note: The agreement between two raters or between two measurement times for one rater can be measured.	REA	[1]
Large simple trial	A randomised pragmatic trial characterised by the recruitment of a large number of subjects, broad patient inclusion criteria, multiple study sites, a simplified data collection process and the use of electronic registers. Note: The purposes of this type of trial include detecting small and moderate treatment effects, obtaining data on the practical effectiveness of the treatment and improving the external validity of the findings.	REA	[1]
Licensing	A marketing authorisation for medicines that meet standards of safety, quality, and efficacy.	Regulatory	[1]
Likelihood ratio	A measure of the strength of a diagnostic test to distinguish between persons who do or do not have a target condition. Note 1: A positive likelihood ratio compares the probability of a positive test result in persons with the disease with the probability of a positive test result in persons without the disease. A negative likelihood ratio compares the probability of a negative test result in persons without the disease with the probability of a negative test result in persons with the disease. Note 2: Positive likelihood ratios greater than 10 or negative likelihood ratios less than 0.1 are sometimes judged to provide convincing diagnostic evidence.	REA	[1]

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	<p>Note 3: A positive likelihood ratio is calculated as: sensitivity ÷ (1 minus specificity). A negative likelihood ratio is calculated as: (1 - sensitivity) ÷ specificity.</p> <p>Note 4: In statistics, an alternative meaning of the likelihood ratio exists. It is the ratio of the values of the likelihood function at two different parameter values or under two different data models.</p>		
Longitudinal study	An observational study in which subjects are followed for the same variable(s) over a period of time.	REA	[17]
Low-intervention clinical trial	<p>A clinical trial which fulfils all of the following conditions:</p> <p>1) the investigational medicinal products, excluding placebos, are authorised;</p> <p>2) according to the protocol of the clinical trial,</p> <p>(i) the investigational medicinal products are used in accordance with the terms of the marketing authorisation; or</p> <p>(ii) the use of the investigational medicinal products is evidence-based and supported by published scientific evidence on the safety and efficacy of those investigational medicinal products in any of the Member States concerned; and</p> <p>3) the additional diagnostic or monitoring procedures do not pose more than minimal additional risk or burden to the safety of the subjects compared to normal clinical practice in any Member State concerned.</p>	REA	[15]
Managed entry	<p>A conditional arrangement between manufacturer and payer that enables earlier reimbursement of a health technology to address uncertainty in its performance or to manage its utilisation.</p> <p>See also “Coverage with evidence development”.</p>	Payer/Pricing	[1]
Mantel-Haenszel test	A chi-square test for taking categorical confounding variables into account when doing a weighted sum of the associations in each of the categories, called strata.	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	Note: In meta-analyses, the strata are the various studies included.		
Marketing authorisation	A licence given by a regulatory authority to an applicant allowing for the marketing of a specific product within the jurisdiction of the regulatory agency. The decision for granting a marketing authorisation is based primarily on the quality, safety and efficacy of the new medicinal product and is based on the evidence of a positive benefit/risk ratio at the time of approval, i.e., the expected benefits outweigh the anticipated risks in a defined population, at a defined dosing and dose regimen, with defined conditions of use. See also “Licensing”.	Regulatory	[17]
Marketing authorisation holder (MAH)	The company or other legal entity that has the authorisation to market a medicine in one, several or all European Union member states. See also “Marketing authorisation”.	Regulatory	[11]
Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC)	A probabilistic analysis method combined with the Markov model, which captures the transitional probabilities between various states to study the interaction between the probability distributions attached to each variable. Note: This type of simulation provides an estimate of the degree of uncertainty in a model. It is widely used in Bayesian analysis to build or update models of the joint distribution of variables.	CEA	[1]
Markov model	A type of quantitative modelling that involves a specified set of mutually exclusive and exhaustive health states for which there are transitional probabilities of moving from one state to another, including the probability of remaining in the same state. Note: Typically, states have a uniform time period, and transitional probabilities remain constant over time.	CEA	[1]
Matching-adjusted indirect	A novel technique allowing for a robust comparison, by re-weighting individual patient data (IPD) from one study to the baseline summary statistics of another, to provide greater adjustment for observed trial differences compared to conventional meta-analytic methods	REA	[35,36]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
comparison (MAIC)	that may be subject to bias due to failing to capture cross-trial differences in patients' baseline characteristics or outcome definitions.		
Measurement bias	A bias introduced by incorrect measurement of the exposure or outcome status of participants in a study. Note: Measurement bias can be introduced by the observer, the study participants or the measurement tools. Synonyms: “information bias” and “observation bias”.	REA; CEA	[1]
Medical device	A medical device is any instrument, apparatus, appliance, or related article that is intended for use in the diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, treatment, or alleviation of disease or that is intended to affect the structure or function of the human anatomy.	Health Technology	[37]
Meta-analysis	A statistical combination of results from multiple studies to obtain a single estimate of the effect of a particular intervention or variable. Note: The meta-analysis appropriately weights each included study according to its precision and, when RCTs are included, it maintains the randomisation of the individual included studies.	REA	[1]
Meta-regression	In a meta-analysis, a regression model for studying the relationship between the different study characteristics and the estimation of the effect observed in these studies. Note: The study characteristics are, for example, the method of distribution into the groups, the type of blinding, the initial risk and the intervention administration schedule.	REA	[1]
Methodological uncertainty	A specific type of uncertainty that relates to methodological choices that are part of economic evaluation. These include the study perspective, discount rate(s), time horizon, the way health effects are valued, and so on. Methodological choices often relate to both the disease and the research question, but are often based on local guidelines, and many aspects of methodological uncertainty can be resolved by making use of a ‘reference case’.	CEA	[38]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Micro-simulation	A form of economic modelling where modelled individuals are passed through the model one by one, their results are stored and then the experience of a cohort is obtained by aggregating the individual results. This is in contrast to most Markov modelling, where the full cohort's experience is considered in a single pass through the model. Micro-simulation models are particularly useful when individuals have a mix of interrelated (and potentially changing) risk factors that influence their experience of a (chronic) disease over time, or where interactions between individuals are important (e.g. infectious disease). Although more complex to create, they may have more general application (than cohort Markov models), in particular being applicable to cohorts with different characteristics (risk factor mix) at the start of the modelled period.	CEA	[7]
Minimally Clinically Important Differences (MCID)	When assessing the clinical utility of therapies intended to improve subjective outcomes, the amount of improvement that is important to patients must be determined. The smallest benefit of value to patients is called the minimal clinically important difference (MCID). The MCID is a patient-centred concept, capturing both the magnitude of the improvement and the value patients place on the change. Using patient-centred MCIDs is important for studies involving patient-reported outcomes, for which the clinical importance of a given change may not be obvious to clinicians selecting treatments. The MCID defines the smallest amount an outcome must change to be meaningful to patients.	REA	[7]
Misclassification	The classification of a person or a characteristic as being in a category other than that to which it should have been assigned, leading to a measurement bias.	REA; CEA	[1]
Misclassification bias	Possibility of error associated with the classification of study participants with regards to their exposure status, outcome status, or disease status. Random occurrence of information bias is known as 'non-differential misclassification' while non-random occurrence is known as 'differential misclassification'. Misclassification bias falls within the category of information bias.	REA; CEA	[4]
Missing values	Missing values occur when no data value is stored for a variable of interest in a study observation. In most study datasets, there are missing values, and the amount and type of	REA; CEA	[7]

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	<p>missing values can have an important impact on the conclusions that can be drawn from the data. If the likelihood of data being missing is related a. to the study outcome or b. to other explanatory variables, then the study results will be biased. For example, if the prevalence of a health condition is related to age and older people are less likely to report whether they have the condition (a) then the study will under-report the prevalence of the condition. If older people are less likely to provide their age (b), then the study will under-report the relationship between the health condition and age. Data are classified as ‘missing completely at random’ (MCAR) if the chances of them being missing are independent of observable variables and of unobservable parameters of interest. In this case, the analysis will not be biased (but will be more uncertain). Data are (somewhat confusingly) called ‘missing at random’ (MAR) if the chances of them being missing are not associated directly with the outcome of interest but may be accounted for by variables for which there is complete information. Otherwise, missing data are ‘missing not at random’ (MNAR). For MNAR and MAR, it is important to understand the patterns of missingness and to use appropriate statistical techniques to control for possible bias (in the case of MAR, some statistical analyses may be unbiased). Simple exclusion of study subjects with missing values will usually maintain or increase the bias in the results. Typical methods used to adjust for missing values include imputation (various methods exist), partial deletion, inverse propensity weighting or more complicated maximum likelihood estimation. In economic modelling, sensitivity analysis may be used to explore the impact of ‘best case’ and ‘worst case’ assumptions about missing data in source studies.</p>		
Mixed treatment comparisons	<p>Mixed treatment comparisons are statistical methods for meta-analysis allowing for the comparison of the relative effects of multiple treatments, even without the presence of a common comparator against which all interventions are studied.</p> <p>See also “Network meta-analysis”.</p>	REA	[4]
Mobile health (mHealth)	<p>The application of mobile technologies in healthcare.</p> <p>Note: Examples of mHealth technologies include wearable devices and mobile medical applications.</p>	Health Technology	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	See also “Digital health”.		
Monte Carlo simulation	<p>A technique used in computer simulation that serves to generate probabilistic outcomes of a model repeatedly and that, for all the simulations, provides a randomly chosen value for each variable on the basis of each distribution of the input parameters.</p> <p>Note: For example, a Monte Carlo simulation can be used to represent or model many individual patients in a population with ranges of values for certain health characteristics or clinical outcomes. In some cases, the random components are added to the values of a known input variable to determine the effects of fluctuations of this variable on the values of the output variable.</p>	CEA	[1]
Mortality rate	<p>The proportion of deaths in a given population within a specified period (usually one year).</p> <p>Note: The rate is often expressed as a number per 100,000 to facilitate interpretation (e.g., 18.3 deaths per year per 100,000 persons).</p>	REA	[1]
Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA)	<p>Multi-criteria decision analysis is a domain of operational research that is beginning to be used in healthcare decision-making. The technique recognises that decision-makers use multiple and disparate criteria when making decisions (for example, about introducing new health care interventions or facilities, etc.) and that it is important to make explicit the impact on any decision of all the criteria applied and the relative importance attached to them. In MCDA, criteria affecting a decision are identified and weighted using explicit, transparent techniques. Then, different options (strategies, interventions, etc.) are scored against each criterion, and the weights are used to provide summary scores for comparative purposes. MCDA has been found to be attractive in health technology assessment, especially in healthcare systems where there is a reluctance to primarily use a single decision metric (such as the ICER). It helps to make more transparent assumptions underpinning decisions, which, in principle, may improve accountability and consistency of decision-making. There are some technical issues around defining and weighting decision criteria scoring performance against criteria for healthcare</p>	HTA decision-making	[7]

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	interventions, which have resulted in its uptake in healthcare being quite slow. One area of recent application is benefit-risk analysis.		
Multi-state transition model	Multi-state transition models are used to model prognosis for clinical problems with ongoing risks. The model assumes that the patient is always in one of a finite number of clinical conditions, referred to as states. All events of interest are modelled as transitions from one state to another. Multi-state transition models can be either discrete or continuous time models. For the former, the transitions are only possible at certain time points. The time interval from one time point to the next one is referred to as a cycle. The net probability of making a transition from one state to another during a single cycle is called transition probability. This transition probability can be constant over time or not. In a model comprising n states, for example, all possible transition probabilities can be encoded in an (n×n) transition matrix. Multi-state transition models can model a cohort of patients or individuals. In the latter case, they are called microsimulation models. A prominent example is the illness-death model with three states representing health, illness and death.	CEA	[4]
Multi-way sensitivity analysis	Multi-way sensitivity analysis is a technique that accounts for the fact that more than one parameter in a model is uncertain, and the output of the model is sensitive to the choice of value for each of these parameters (commonly the key parameters in the model). During multi-way sensitivity analysis, the value of each parameter is changed simultaneously, and the impact that this has on the model output is investigated. This technique is limited to investigating the impact of changing relatively few (2 to 5) parameters simultaneously, given that the number of possible combinations of parameter values has the potential to get very large.	CEA	[7]
Multilevel network meta-regression	Multilevel network meta-regression is a flexible and general method for synthesising evidence from mixtures of individual and aggregate-level data in networks of all sizes. See also “Network meta-regression”.	REA	[39]
Multiple testing	Several statistical tests done on the same observations.	REA	[1]

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	<p>Note: In a study, the sample size and the alpha level are set according to the principle that a single null hypothesis will be tested at the end of the study once all the data have been gathered. If more than one statistical test is undertaken, e.g., pairwise comparisons of several interventions, or tests on different variables, at different timepoints or on different sub-groups, there will be an increase in the planned overall Type I error (alpha) probability. Some statistical methods are proposed to take multiple testing into account, but they are controversial.</p>		
Multiplicative model	<p>A model in which the combined effect of two or more factors is the product of the isolated effects of each factor.</p> <p>Note: For example, if a factor X multiplies a risk by a in the absence of Y, and if a second factor Y multiplies the risk by b in the absence of X, the combined effect of the two factors will be $a \times b$.</p>	REA; CEA	[1]
Multiplicity	<p>A feature of certain inferential problems that arise in clinical trials with multiple objectives (e.g. the investigation of several treatments, subgroups or clinical endpoint), or if a series of hypotheses are tested. If not accounted for, multiplicity can increase the probability of making a type-1 error and confound the interpretation of statistical inferences made.</p>	REA; CEA	[14]
n of 1 trial	<p>A clinical trial in which a single subject is the total population for the study.</p> <p>Note: Random allocation may be used to determine the order in which the subject will receive the experimental intervention and the control intervention.</p>	REA	[1]
Natural history	<p>The course of a disease from onset to resolution.</p> <p>Note: Many diseases have well-defined stages, such as the pathological onset, presymptomatic and clinically manifest disease stages.</p>	REA	[1]
Negative predictive value (NPV)	<p>A test performance characteristic, defined as the proportion of persons who do not have the disease among those who have a negative diagnostic test result; it is calculated as follows: $\text{true negatives} \div (\text{true negatives} + \text{false negatives})$.</p>	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	Note: The NPV varies with the prevalence of the disease in the population of interest. See also “Positive predictive value (PPV)”.		
Net benefit	The benefit of an option in monetary units minus its total cost in monetary units. Note: Net benefit is a basic decision criterion in Cost-benefit analysis (CBA).	CEA	[1]
Network meta-analysis	An extension of meta-analysis allowing for the comparison of the relative effects of multiple treatments, either with or without the presence of a common comparator against which all interventions are studied. Network meta-analysis methods take into account direct and indirect treatment comparisons and pairwise meta-analysis. See also “Direct treatment comparison” and “Indirect treatment comparison”.	REA	[17]
New health technology	A health technology that is in the launch, early post-marketing or early diffusion stages. See also “Health technology” and “Emerging health technology”.	Health Technology	[1]
Non-Inferiority Study	A non-inferiority study is one where the aim is to show that the effectiveness of one technology is not inferior to a comparator technology by a clinically important amount. This non-inferiority margin (M2: also called the ‘preserved fraction’ or ‘degree of inferiority’) is the percentage of the effect size of the current or comparator technology against a placebo comparator (M1) that is clinically acceptable to be maintained for non-inferiority to be assumed. M1 and M2 need to be established prior to a study to allow sample size to be calculated with sufficient power to support a conclusion that the intervention technology is non-inferior or equivalent to the comparator. Particular attention needs to be paid to the derivation of M1 and M2 and the quality of the study design and execution. Unlike for superiority studies, intention-to-treat analyses are unlikely to be conservative (per protocol analyses may need to be performed), and statistical hypothesis testing may need to be one-sided at the 2.5% level. Non-inferiority and clinical equivalence studies have become more common in recent years for interventions where placebo comparators cannot be used for ethical reasons, or where there is interest by healthcare payers in establishing the comparative effectiveness of a new technology.	REA	[7]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Non-randomised controlled trial	<p>A study comparing interventions in which the allocation of participants to the control and intervention groups is not based on chance.</p> <p>Note 1: Examples include allocation based on alternating groups, the investigator's practical constraints, or the participant's choice.</p> <p>Note 2: A non-randomised controlled trial is different from an observational study and a non-experimental study.</p> <p>Synonyms include Non-randomised controlled trial, Non-randomised comparative study or trial, Non-randomised intervention study or trial, and Non-randomised clinical trial.</p>	REA	[1]
Number needed to treat	<p>The number of subjects treated per subject with a favourable outcome.</p> <p>Note: It is the inverse of absolute risk reduction ($1 \div \text{absolute risk reduction}$). Thus, if the results of a study indicate that the probability of death in a control group is 25% and the probability of death in a treatment group is 10%, the number needed to treat would be $1.0 \div (0.25 - 0.10) = 6.7$, therefore 7 subjects.</p> <p>See also "Absolute risk reduction", "Relative risk reduction", and "Odds ratio".</p>	REA	[1]
Observational data	<p>Data collected from patient populations as present in the routine setting of healthcare (i.e., outside the setting of a randomised controlled trial). Sources of observational data include: routine clinical practice, patient registries, hospital claims databases/administrative data, health surveys, electronic health records, medical chart reviews and post-marketing safety studies.</p>	REA; CEA	[4]
Observational study	<p>A study in which the investigators do not intervene, but only observe subjects who are (and sometimes who are not, for comparison purposes) exposed to a given factor, and interpret the outcomes.</p> <p>Note: This type of study is more subject to bias than an experimental study such as a randomised controlled trial.</p>	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Odds	The ratio (quotient) of the probability that an event will occur to the probability that this event will not occur.	REA	[1]
Odds ratio (OR)	<p>The ratio (quotient) of the exposure odds among the cases (subjects who are ill or have died, for example) to that among the controls (subjects who are not ill or who are alive, for example).</p> <p>Note: The odds ratio is the estimate of relative risk used in a type of study (case-control) in which it is impossible to calculate relative risk directly. It is a good estimate of relative risk in cases in which the disease is rare. Thus, if the results of a trial are that the probability of death is 25% in the control group and 10% in the experimental group, the odds ratio of survival is $[0.10 \div (1.0 - 0.10)] \div [(0.25 \div (1.0 - 0.25))] = 0.33$.</p> <p>See also “Absolute risk reduction”, “Number needed to treat”, and “Relative risk”.</p>	REA	[1]
Open-label trial	<p>A clinical trial in which the investigator and the subject know who is receiving which intervention.</p> <p>Note: This term is also used when only one intervention is being studied, for unblinded long-term follow-up studies or when blinding is difficult or unethical (comparison of a surgical treatment and a medical treatment, for example).</p>	REA	[1]
Opportunity cost	The value of the benefits of a better option that is given up when another option is chosen.	CEA	[1]
Orphan medicinal product	A medicine for the diagnosis, prevention or treatment of a life-threatening or chronically debilitating condition that is rare (affecting not more than five in 10,000 people in the European Union) or where the medicine is unlikely to generate sufficient profit to justify research and development costs.	Health Technology	[17]
Out-of-pocket payments	Payments made by a health care consumer that are not reimbursed by a third party payer. They include cost-sharing and informal payments to healthcare providers.	CEA, Payer/Pricing	[3]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Outcomes-based arrangements	An agreement that defines how to demonstrate product value, while mitigating financial risk and considering real-world factors, such as medication adherence or complex comorbidities that may influence the effectiveness of a treatment. The performance of the product is measured in a defined patient cohort over a finite period of time using a key outcome.	HTA decision-making; Payer/Pricing	[17]
P value	In hypothesis testing, the probability that a parameter to be tested has a value as extreme or more extreme than the value that would be observed if the null hypothesis were true. Note: If the p value associated with the statistical test is equal to or greater than the alpha level that was determined (0.01 or 0.05, for example), this means that the association or difference observed may be due to chance and that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. However, if the p value is less than the alpha level that was determined, the association or difference is statistically significant, and the null hypothesis is rejected. Alternate spelling: p-value	REA; CEA	[1]
PICO	PICO stands for population, intervention, comparator and outcomes	REA; CEA; Other HTA elements	[40]
PICOTS	PICOTS stands for population, intervention, comparator, outcomes, timing and setting	REA; CEA; Other HTA elements	[20]
Parallel group trial	A trial that compares two contemporaneous groups, one receiving the treatment of interest, the other being the control group (in a randomised clinical trial, for example). Note: Some of these trials have more than one treatment group; others compare two treatment groups, each being a control for the other.	REA	[1]
Parameter uncertainty	The uncertainty in the estimation of the parameter(s) of interest. Parameter uncertainty has also been called second-order uncertainty. Parameter uncertainty may be represented via deterministic (DSA) or probabilistic sensitivity analysis (PSA).	CEA	[41]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Patient advocates	Persons who have the insight and experience in supporting a larger population of patients living with a specific disease. They may or may not be affiliated with an organisation.	Other HTA elements	[42]
Patient awareness	The degree to which a patient or group of patients have knowledge about treatment options	Other HTA elements	[17]
Patient experts	In addition to disease-specific expertise, they have technical knowledge in R&D and/or regulatory affairs through training or experience. For example, EUPATI fellows who have been trained by EUPATI on the full spectrum of medicines R&D.	Other HTA elements	[42]
Patient organisation representatives	Persons who are mandated to represent and express the collective views of a patient organisation on a specific issue or disease area.	Other HTA elements	[42]
Patient preferences	Qualitative or quantitative assessments of the relative desirability or acceptability to patients of specified alternatives or choices among outcomes or other attributes that differ among alternative health interventions.	Other HTA elements	[43]
Patient registries	Patient registries are organised systems that use observational methods to collect uniform data on a population defined by a particular disease, condition or exposure, and that is followed over time.	REA; CEA	[43]
Patient relevant outcome	An outcome that is meaningful to the patient, which can be health or non-health related. Examples may include outcomes related to how a patient feels or functions in daily life, quality of life or utility measures, or economic outcomes.	CEA; Other HTA elements	[43]
Patient values	The considerations that are important to an individual patient or group of patients.	CEA; Other HTA elements	[43]
Patient-level simulation model	A patient-level simulation is a type of model in which outcomes are estimated for modelled patients one at a time. In this model, the determination of outcomes is usually based on random (stochastic) selection of patients: a large number of patients are required to be simulated in order to estimate the mean outcomes (and their distribution) for the population	CEA	[7]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	considered in the analysis. The benefits of this type of model over cohort models are that it allows individual patient histories to be recorded, and the model can capture (first-order) heterogeneity in the patient population. They are often considered more intuitive or more flexible than cohort models. One drawback may be the additional computational requirements for the model to run, particularly when running sensitivity analyses.		
Patient-reported experience measure (PREM)	Patient-reported experience measures (PREMs) are psychometrically validated tools (e.g. questionnaires) used to capture patients’ interactions with healthcare systems and the degree to which their needs are being met. PREMs are designed to determine whether patients have experienced certain care processes rather than their satisfaction with the care received (which may be subject to bias). A PREM may, for instance, be used to collect information on the patient's experience with hospital admission. Data derived from this could be used to inform service development and configuration.	Other HTA elements	[7]
Patient-reported outcomes (PROs)	Patient-reported outcomes (PROs) are any reports directly from patients on their health, condition, etc., that are made solely by such patients without any input, suggestions or interpretation from their doctors, family, friends or other individuals. PRO is a blanket term relating to single or multidimensional aspects of patients’ symptoms, health, quality of life, treatment satisfaction, medication adherence, etc. PROs are often recorded in clinical trials using Patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs). See also “Patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs)”.	CEA	[7]
Patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs)	Patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) are standardised questionnaires that contain multiple questions or items, which patients answer on their own to generate numerical scores measuring symptoms, function, perceived health status, and other important unobservable aspects of HRQL. See also “Patient-reported outcomes (PROs)”.	CEA	[44]
Per protocol	An analysis that excludes subjects who were not compliant with the intervention regimen (took prohibited concurrent treatments, for example).	REA	[1]

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	<p>Note: The population of interest is thus highly filtered and not influenced by factors that could dilute the effect of treatment. This form of analysis may therefore produce a larger estimate of the treatment effect.</p> <p>See also “Intention-to-treat analysis”.</p> <p>Other definition:</p> <p>An analysis of the subset of subjects of a randomised controlled trial who have complied with the protocol sufficiently for there to be a good chance that their outcomes demonstrate the effect of the intervention of interest. This subset may be defined on the basis of exposure to the intervention, the availability of measurements and the lack of major departures from the protocol. This analysis strategy may be subject to bias because the non-compliance with the protocol may be due to the intervention.</p>		
Performance bias	<p>A confusion bias due to systematic differences in care received outside the intervention being evaluated.</p> <p>Note: For example, if subjects know which group they are in, they are more likely to use other forms of care. If care providers have the same information, they may treat the subjects differently, according to what group they are in. Blinding (both the recipients and the providers of care) is used to, among other things, protect against performance bias.</p>	REA	[1]
Personalised medicine	<p>A medicine that is targeted to individual patients or a stratified population of patients with specific characteristics.</p> <p>Personalised medicine can also be interpreted more narrowly to mean targeted treatment according to genetic variations only or to mean a unique treatment for the individual patient rather than groups of patients.</p> <p>See also “Precision medicine”.</p>	Health Technology	[17]
Peto method	In a meta-analysis, a method used to combine odds ratios.	REA	[1]

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	Note: The calculations are straightforward and easy to interpret, but the result may sometimes differ substantially from that obtained using other methods. The Peto method is based on a fixed-effect model.		
Pharmacovigilance	Science and activities relating to the detection, assessment, understanding and prevention of adverse effects or any other medicine-related problem.	Regulatory; Post-launch	[11]
Phase-I study	A type of clinical study where a new medicine is given to humans for the first time, usually in healthy volunteers. It looks at the way the medicine is dealt with by the body, its main effects and main side effects.	REA	[11]
Phase-II study	A type of clinical study conducted after phase I studies to evaluate a medicine's effects in a particular condition and to determine its common short-term side effects.	REA	[11]
Phase-III study	A type of clinical study usually conducted in a large group of patients to gather information about a medicine's efficacy and safety, to allow its benefits and risks to be evaluated.	REA	[11]
Phase-IV study	A type of clinical study that takes place after the authorisation of a medicine.	REA	[11]
Placebo	A substance, procedure or treatment used to simulate a therapeutic intervention. Note: In research, a placebo is given to a control group to isolate the true effect of the treatment being studied. See also "Placebo effect".	REA	[1]
Placebo effect	The beneficial response that a patient experiences when exposed to a simulated therapeutic intervention. Note: Sometimes, part of the beneficial response following a therapeutic intervention is due to the placebo effect. Synonym: "Placebo response". See also "Placebo".	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Policymaker	A person or institution that is involved in policy development and formulation (e.g. national governments, public authorities).	HTA decision-making	[3]
Population-adjusted method for indirect comparisons	A method for indirect comparisons in which a mix of individual patient data (IPD) from one or more trials, and aggregate data from other trials, are used to adjust for relevant population characteristics that differ between studies in order to estimate a treatment effect.	REA	[24]
Positive predictive value (PPV)	A test performance characteristic defined as the proportion of persons with a positive result in a diagnostic test who have the disease; it is calculated as follows: true positives ÷ (true positives + false positives). Note: the PPV varies with the prevalence of the disease in the population of interest. See also “Negative predictive value (NPV)”.	REA	[1]
Post launch evidence generation (PLEG)	Post Launch Evidence Generation (PLEG) is an umbrella term for evidence generated after the launch or licensure of a health technology within its approved or intended indication. Its role is not to replace but to complement evidence generation already undertaken for marketing authorisation or HTA appraisal, addressing remaining uncertainties and potentially covering wider questions of disease management and healthcare delivery.	Post-launch	[45]
Post-authorisation efficacy studies (PAES)	PAES of medicinal products are studies subsequently conducted within the authorised therapeutic indication to address well-reasoned scientific uncertainties identified by EU regulators on aspects of the evidence of benefits that should be, or can only be, addressed post-authorisation.	REA; Post-launch, Regulatory	[46]
Power	The probability of a hypothesis test correctly detecting a real effect. Note 1: Power is also the probability of avoiding a type II error and, therefore, corresponds to $(1 - \beta)$.	REA	[1]

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	<p>Note 2: A power analysis may be performed to determine whether a sample size will have sufficient power to reject a false null hypothesis, and so find the effect described by the alternative hypothesis.</p> <p>See also “Hypothesis testing”.</p>		
Pragmatic Review	<p>A pragmatic review is one that adapts the conventional systematic review process to take into consideration the limited time and/or resources available. This is usually achieved by applying additional limits to the search or eligibility criteria.</p> <p>See also “Systematic review”.</p>	REA	[7]
Pragmatic clinical trial	<p>A study comparing several health interventions among a randomised, diverse population representing clinical practice, and measuring a broad range of health outcomes. To ensure generalizability, pragmatic trials should represent the patients to whom the treatment will be applied as best possible. For instance, inclusion criteria would be broad (e.g. allowing co-morbidity, co-medication, wider age range, etc.), the follow-up would not be (or not much) interventional and allowing for treatment switching, etc. Pragmatic clinical trials are a sub-category of large simple trials.</p> <p>See also “Large simple trial”.</p>	REA	[4]
Precision	<p>1) A quality of a point estimate obtained from a set of observations having a small variance.</p> <p>Note 1: A narrow confidence interval around a point estimate indicates a more precise estimate of effect than a wide confidence interval. Note that a precise estimate is not necessarily accurate.</p> <p>2) A measure of the likelihood of random errors in the results of a study, meta-analysis or measurement.</p> <p>Note 2: In a meta-analysis, the weight given to the results of each study in the overall estimate of the effect of an intervention is often based on the precision of each study,</p>	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	<p>which is estimated using the inverse of the variance of the estimate of effect or the sample size.</p> <p>3) In a literature search, the number of relevant citations divided by the total number of citations retrieved, i.e., the proportion of studies meeting the inclusion criteria for a clinical trial register or a literature review.</p> <p>See also “Accuracy”.</p>		
Precision medicine	The ability to classify individuals into subpopulations that differ in their susceptibility to a particular disease, in the biology and/or prognosis of those diseases they may develop, or in their response to a specific treatment in order to better match patients with therapies.	Health Technology	[17]
Prediction interval	In a random-effects meta-analysis, a $100(1 - \alpha)\%$ prediction interval indicates that the true effect sizes in $100(1 - \alpha)\%$ of new studies will lie within the interval.	REA	[21]
Predictive biomarker	A biomarker used to identify individuals who are more likely than similar individuals without the biomarker to experience a favourable or unfavourable effect from exposure to a medical product or an environmental agent.	REA	[14]
Predictive modelling	The process by which a model is created or chosen to try to best predict the probability of an outcome.	REA	[47]
Preference-based measures (PBM)	Preference-based measures (PBM) or generic preference-based measures are increasingly used in health economic evaluations to calculate quality-adjusted life years (QALYs). Such measures usually comprise a number of domains (or descriptive sets) that patients can use to describe various aspects of their health (e.g. limitations in daily activities and mobility, pain and discomfort). These patient-reported values (profile scores) are then converted to an index score using a selected algorithm (sometimes country-specific). These algorithms are based on surveying the general public’s preferences for different combinations of health states, which is why these measures are referred to as “preference-based”. The index scores (sometimes called ‘utilities’) usually range between 0 and 1, where 1 is usually taken to reflect a valuation of “perfect health”, and 0 refers to a	CEA	[7]

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	valuation of “death”. In some of these measures values below zero may be possible, representing health states perceived to be worse than death. Examples of PBMs include the EQ-5D, SF-6D and the Health Utilities Index.		
Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA)	Preferred reporting items are the reporting items deemed by the PRISMA group to be essential for maintaining a minimum level of reporting quality in systematic reviews and meta-analyses. They are detailed on the 27-item PRISMA checklist and are split into the sections: title, abstract, introduction, methods, results, discussion and funding. Each category contains guidance on the minimum information points (“items”) that should be reported in each section of a report or manuscript to ensure a consistent minimum standard of reporting.	REA	[7]
Prevalence	The number of people in a population with a specific disease or condition at a given time, usually expressed as a proportion of the number of affected people to the total population.	REA; CEA	[1]
Price volume agreement	Agreements which focus on controlling financial expenditure with pharmaceutical companies refunding over-budget situations. See also “Managed entry”.	Payer/Pricing; Post-launch	[3]
Priority setting	The assignment of an order of priority based on explicit or implicit criteria for the selection of health technologies for assessment.	HTA decision-making	[1]
Probabilistic sensitivity analysis (PSA)	Probabilistic sensitivity analysis (PSA) is a technique used in economic modelling that allows the modeller to quantify the level of confidence in the output of the analysis, in relation to uncertainty in the model inputs. There is usually uncertainty associated with input parameter values of an economic model, which may have been derived from clinical trials, observational studies or, in some cases, expert opinion. In the base case analysis, the point estimate of each input parameter value is used. In the probabilistic analysis, these parameters are represented as distributions around the point estimate, which can be summarised using a few parameters (such as mean and standard deviation for a normal distribution). In a PSA, a set of input parameter values is drawn by random sampling from each distribution, and the model is ‘run’ to generate outputs (cost and health outcome),	CEA	[7]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	which are stored. This is repeated many times (typically 1,000 to 10,000), resulting in a distribution of outputs that can be graphed on the cost-effectiveness plane and analysed.		
Propensity scores	Propensity scores are used to estimate the effect of receiving treatment when random assignment of treatments to subjects is not feasible. The estimated propensity score for a subject is the conditional probability of being assigned to a particular treatment given a vector of observed covariates.	REA	[48]
Propensity-based trials	Clinical trials involving the allocation of subjects to intervention groups on the basis of propensity scores. These propensity scores are, in turn, based upon a vector of observed covariates. See also “Propensity score”.	REA	[4]
Prospective study	A study to evaluate the effects of exposure to a given intervention or factor, in which the subjects are divided into groups that are exposed or not exposed to the intervention or factor of interest before the outcomes have occurred. Note: Randomised controlled trials are always prospective, but case-control studies never are. Cohort studies may be prospective or retrospective. Related concept: Cohort study. †Antonym: Retrospective study. † A cohort study may be a prospective study, but a prospective study is not necessarily a cohort study: a cohort study involves a methodology, i.e. comparison, that is not necessarily common to all prospective studies. The qualifier “prospective,” without further details, indicates only the study’s temporal direction.	REA	[1]
Protocol	The plan or set of steps to be followed in a study. Note: For example, a protocol for a systematic review must describe the purpose of the review, its objectives and the methods to be used to locate, select and critically appraise the included studies, and to collect and analyse data from them.	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Publication bias	A bias due to studies being published based on the nature and direction of their results. Example: a study with statistically significant results favouring the intervention of interest may have a greater likelihood of being published.	REA	[1]
Quality assurance	A method combining all the predetermined and systematic actions needed to provide appropriate confidence that a product or service will meet given quality requirements. Note: Quality assurance includes setting and applying healthcare standards based on the best available knowledge, and this involves quality assessment and activities to correct and reduce variations in healthcare practices relative to these standards, or to improve those practices.	Other HTA elements	[1]
Quality-adjusted life year (QALY)	A unit of outcome of an intervention where gains (or losses) of years of life subsequent to this intervention are adjusted on the basis of the quality of life during those years. Note: This parameter can provide a common unit for comparing cost-utility across different interventions and health problems. Disability-adjusted life year (DALY) and Healthy-years equivalent (HYE) are QALY-analogous units.	CEA	[1]
Quasi-randomisation	The allocation of clinical trial participants to an intervention or control group using methods that are not truly random but still intended to produce similar groups. Note 1: Examples include allocation based on date of birth, medical record number, or the order in which participants were recruited. Note 2: Quasi-randomisation is used when true randomisation is not feasible.	REA	[1]
Random error	A deviation due to chance between a point estimate and the value of the estimated parameter. Note: Random error leads to about the same number of results greater than the true value sought and results lower than this value. It is independent of the effects of systematic biases. In general, the larger the mean sample size is, the smaller the random error is.	REA; CEA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Random-effects model	<p>In a meta-analysis, a statistical model in which both the within-study variance and the between-studies variances are included in the assessment of the degree of uncertainty (confidence interval) of the combined effect of the studies.</p> <p>Note: If there is significant heterogeneity among the results of the studies included in a meta-analysis, a random effects model will give wider confidence intervals than a fixed-effect model.</p> <p>See also “Fixed-effect model”.</p>	REA	[1]
Randomisation	<p>The random allocation of subjects of a clinical trial to the intervention and control groups using mechanisms such as a random number table or a computer-generated random number list.</p> <p>Note: This type of allocation reduces potential bias in subject assignment because it tends to neutralise known and unknown prognostic factors by spreading them evenly between the intervention and control groups. Randomisation is a basic condition for the validity of many statistical tests. Non-random systematic allocation, or quasi-randomisation, which allocates the subjects on the basis of elements such as day of the week, name, date of birth, etc., is not equivalent to randomisation and can lead to serious biases.</p> <p>See also “Blinding”.</p> <p>Alternate spelling: Randomization.</p>	REA	[1]
Randomised controlled trial (RCT)	<p>A clinical trial designed to test the efficacy and/or safety of an intervention within a sample of selected subjects, who are subjected to predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria and randomly assigned to two or more groups (at least one treatment and one control group).</p>	REA	[17]
Rapid review	<p>A report that usually includes a review of the highest level of evidence or of recent evidence and that may restrict the literature to one or two databases.</p> <p>Note 1: The report always:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • describes the characteristics and current use of the technology and 	REA; CEA	[1]

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> evaluates safety and effectiveness issues <p>Note 2: The report does not always critically appraise the quality of the evidence base or provide information on costs and financial impact.</p> <p>Note 3: A rapid review is typically not as rigorous as a mini-HTA or a HTA report but is quicker to produce.</p> <p>See also “Health technology assessment” and “HTA report”.</p>		
Rate	A measure of the frequency of occurrence of a phenomenon. In epidemiology, demography, and vital statistics, a rate is an expression of the frequency with which an event occurs in a defined population in a specified period of time. The use of rates rather than raw numbers is essential for the comparison of experience between populations at different times, different places, or among different classes of persons.	REA	[3]
Real world data (RWD)	Data collected during the routine delivery of health care. Note: Sources may include observational data, administrative data, research data, patient-generated data or professional-generated data. These data may be collected in administrative datasets, case notes, surveys, product and disease registries, social media, electronic health records, claims and billing datasets, or mobile health applications.	REA; CEA	[1]
Real world evidence (RWE)	Evidence derived from the analysis of real world data. Note: Real world data are primarily analysed through observational study designs. This real world evidence is characterised by the actual use of the technology in practice and by findings that are generalisable to the target population for the technology.	REA; CEA	[1]
Real world study (RWS)	See “Effectiveness study”.	REA; CEA	[4]
Reference case	A ‘reference case’ is used by some health technology assessment bodies to summarise their guidance to those making and assessing submissions for reimbursement. The reference case gives a formal statement of accepted methods and assumptions	CEA	[7]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	underpinning analyses to which submissions should conform. The purpose is to ensure a level of consistency between submissions and assessments of evidence.		
Reference standard	The benchmark against which the performance of other tests, procedures or investigations are compared. Synonyms include “gold standard” and “standard of care”.	REA; CEA	[1]
Referral bias	Referral bias occurs if reasons for referring a patient to a health intervention/ health care institute are related to the drug exposure status, e.g., when the use of the drug contributes to the diagnostic process. This sort of bias falls within the category of selection bias. See also “Selection bias”	REA	[4]
Regression analysis	A method consisting of selecting a mathematical model (linear or logistic regression, for example) that explains the data to describe or predict the effect of one or more independent variables X on a dependent variable Y. Note: The terms are used as follows: linear regression when the variable Y is continuous, logistic regression when Y is a dichotomous variable, simple regression when there is a single variable X, and multiple regression when there are several variables X.	REA; CEA	[1]
Relative effectiveness	The extent to which an intervention does more good than harm, when compared to one or more intervention alternatives for achieving the desired results and when provided under the routine setting of health care practice (i.e., real world setting).	REA	[4]
Relative efficacy	The extent to which an intervention does more good than harm when compared to one or more alternative interventions under ideal conditions (i.e. highly-controlled conditions of a randomised controlled trial).	REA	[4]
Relative risk (RR)	The ratio (quotient) of the risk that an event will occur among the subjects exposed to a given factor and the risk that this event will occur among the subjects not exposed to this factor.	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	<p>Note: A relative risk (RR) of 1 indicates that the risk is equal in the groups compared, an RR > 1 indicates that the factor increases the risk, and an RR < 1 indicates that the factor decreases the risk.</p> <p>Synonyms: “Risk ratio”.</p>		
Relative risk reduction	<p>The ratio (quotient) of the risk difference for the occurrence of an event in the group exposed to a given factor and the probability that this event will occur in the group not exposed to this factor.</p> <p>Note: Thus, if the results of a trial show that the probability of death is 25% in the control group and 10% in the experimental group, the relative risk reduction is $(0.25 - 0.10) \div 0.25 = 0.6$.</p> <p>See also “Absolute risk reduction”, “Number needed to treat”, and “Odds ratio”.</p>	REA	[1]
Reliability	<p>1) The ability of an examination or test, done repeatedly and in the same population, to produce the same result (test-retest reliability). 2) The ability of a single examination or test to always make the same distinction among individuals in a given population.</p>	REA	[1]
Reporting bias	<p>Reporting bias is the tendency for authors to selectively use information or outcomes from investigations or trials, based on certain characteristics. The dissemination of research findings may therefore be influenced by the nature and direction of the results. Different types of bias due to the nature and direction of results include: “publication bias” – likelihood of publication of research; “time lag bias” – delaying or expediting publication of research; “citation bias” – citing or not citing research, and “outcome reporting bias” – selective reporting of outcomes. Recently, there have been initiatives such as clinicaltrials.gov to minimise this type of bias, by ensuring that clinical trials (especially those of new medicines, for which marketing authorisation will be sought) are entered prospectively on registers so that their status and results are available, especially for systematic reviews of efficacy supporting health technology assessment.</p>	REA	[7]
Resource use	<p>Resource use refers to the use of healthcare staff time, facilities, or consumables (especially medicines). In clinical trials and other studies, health care costs are frequently</p>	CEA	[7]

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	<p>estimated by counting items of resource that are used by study subjects and by associating these with relevant costs for each resource unit for the country of interest. In see for service systems such as the US, charges may be recorded, which can be converted to costs using cost-to-charge ratios. Commonly recorded items of resource use are GP or specialist visits, hospital admissions (often classified by diagnostic-related group) or hospital bed days (often classified by intensity of ward care), and medications administered (by dosage, frequency, route of administration). These may be recorded as one-off events or aggregated over a time period (month or year) for use in economic modelling. Resource use and unit cost data are available from many sources, and judgements may be needed as to which data are most suitable for use in a particular context. This is usually based on the assessment of data quality and the similarity of the source (study) to the situation to which the resource use and unit costs will be applied. Resource use data collected in clinical trials may be of limited value for economic evaluations because of the inclusion of protocol-related elements (study visits, care in specialist centres), which may not be representative of routine care. Also, trials are frequently performed in a variety of countries where care patterns and resource definitions may differ.</p>		
Retrospective study	<p>A study in which the investigators do an ex-post analysis of the outcomes in a group of subjects selected on the basis of their exposure to a given intervention or factor.</p> <p>Note: This type of study is more subject to bias than are prospective studies. Case-control studies are always retrospective, cohort studies sometimes are, and randomised controlled trials never are.</p> <p>Antonym: Prospective study.</p>	REA	[1]
Revealed preference	<p>A preference deduced from the choices that an individual makes.</p> <p>Note: Preferences may be revealed by choices made in a natural setting or by responses to an investigator's questions.</p>	Other HTA elements	[1]
Risk	The probability that an event, generally adverse, will occur.	REA	[1]

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	<p>Note: This probability can be estimated as the proportion of persons in a group for whom an event occurs.</p> <p>See also “Risk factor”.</p>		
Risk factor	<p>A factor associated with the occurrence of a health problem.</p> <p>Note: It may be personal behaviour, lifestyle, exposure to environmental hazards, congenital or hereditary characteristics, etc. For example, smoking is a risk factor for lung cancer.</p>	REA	[1]
Risk of bias (RoB)	<p>Assessing the risk of bias in the primary studies acknowledges the varying quality of included studies and is used to guide the interpretation of findings and determine the extent to which inferences can be made from the results. The impact of including low, medium and high-quality studies could be assessed in an investigation of heterogeneity. Quality assessment tools are numerous and specific to the type of study design. Some agencies will specify the tool to be used in the systematic reviews they commission/review, and other agencies will be open to discussion about the quality assessment tool to be used.</p>	REA	[7]
Safety	<p>A judgment concerning the acceptability of the risk (a measure of the probability of an adverse outcome and its severity) associated with using a technology in a given situation (e.g. for a patient with a particular health problem) by a clinician with certain training, or in a specified treatment setting.</p>	REA	[1]
Sample size	<p>The number of subjects studied, including those in the intervention group and the control group, where applicable.</p> <p>Note: In general, a large sample size decreases the probability of Type I (α) (false-positive) errors and increases the statistical power of the trial, i.e. decreases the probability of Type II (β) (false-negative) errors. A large sample size decreases the effect of random variation on the estimate of a treatment effect. In designing a study, the desired sample size can be calculated using a statistical formula based on the acceptable levels of α and β</p>	REA; CEA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	errors, the smallest difference between intervention groups considered clinically relevant, and the measurement variance.		
Scientific advisory group (EU)	A group of European experts brought together to provide advice in connection with the evaluation of specific medicines.	Regulatory	[11]
Scientific advice (EU)	The provision of scientific advice for medicines and medical devices. For medicines, the European Medicines Agency (EMA) advises on the appropriate tests and studies required in the development or quality of a medicine. For medical devices, the expert panels created by the European Commission advise on clinical studies required in the development of high-risk medical devices.	Regulatory	[11]
Screening	A public health service in which members of a population at risk for a disease or its complications are asked questions or offered a test, to identify those individuals who are at sufficiently high risk that further diagnostic tests or treatments are justified.	Health Technology	[1]
Selection bias	A type of bias due to an error in the estimation of the effect of an intervention because of the way in which the subjects were selected in the population of interest. Note: There is selection bias in cohort studies if the recruitment of the subjects who are exposed (not exposed) is linked to the presence of the disease. In case-control studies, selection bias occurs if the recruitment of the cases (controls) is linked to exposure to the factor of interest.	REA	[1]
Self-selection bias	Occurs when study participants decide themselves to participate in or to leave a study based on both drug exposure and change in health status. This sort of bias falls within the category of selection bias. See also “Selection bias”.	REA	[4]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Sensitivity	<p>A characteristic of the performance of a diagnostic test, defined as the proportion of persons who have a positive test result among the persons who have the disease; it is calculated as follows: true positives ÷ (true positives + false negatives).</p> <p>See also “Accuracy” and “Specificity”.</p>	REA	[1]
Sensitivity analysis	<p>A means for evaluating the robustness of a mathematical model by testing a plausible range of estimates of key independent variables to determine whether such variations result in meaningful changes in the model’s results.</p> <p>Note: Sensitivity analysis can also be used for other study types, such as clinical trials analysis, to determine whether inclusion or exclusion of certain data changes the results, and meta-analysis, to determine whether inclusion or exclusion of certain studies changes the results.</p>	REA; CEA	[1]
Sequential trial	<p>A statistical method that allows for ending an experiment as soon as a response with the desired precision is obtained, with each outcome being examined as soon as it occurs and being added to all the previous outcomes.</p> <p>Note: The main advantage of a sequential trial is as follows:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) it is shorter than a fixed-length trial when there is a large difference in the effectiveness of the interventions being compared; or 2) a trial can be terminated quickly when there is a health risk. Since, with this approach, the assignment of the treatments generally must be known before the study, special methods for the analysis and dissemination of interim results are required. <p>See also “Meta-analysis”.</p>	REA	[1]
Short Form 36 (SF-36)	<p>Short Form 36 (SF-36) is a questionnaire used to measure the health status of particular populations to help service planning and also measure the impact of clinical and social interventions. The questionnaire generates scores for eight domains of health status: physical functioning, physical role limitations, bodily pains, general health perceptions, vitality, social functioning, emotional role limitations and mental health. These scores are</p>	REA; CEA	[49]

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	then transformed to a range from zero, the worst possible health, to 100, the best possible health. While such domain scores provide a means to measure the effectiveness of an intervention, they cannot be used to conduct a cost-utility analysis because they are not based on preferences. See also “Short Form 6 Dimensions (SF-6D)”.		
Short Form 6 Dimensions (SF-6D)	SF-6D is a preference-based instrument that is based on Short Form 36. The SF-6D was developed as a tool to convert the results of studies that used the SF-36 questionnaire to health state preference values needed to calculate QALYs. The instrument consists of a multi-attribute health status classification system with six attributes (physical functioning, role limitations, social functioning, pain, mental health and vitality) and a scoring table, which contains scores for each of the attributes. See “Short Form 36 (SF-36)”.	CEA	[49]
Simulated treatment comparison (STC)	Simulated treatment comparison (STC) is a method for performing population adjustment for the indirect comparison of two treatments, where individual patient data (IPD) are available for one trial, but only aggregate level information is available for the other.	REA	[50]
Single-arm study	An analysis or evaluation of a study with only one branch, i.e., a trial in which there was no parallel comparison group and all the subjects received the same intervention.	REA	[1]
Specificity	A characteristic of the performance of a diagnostic test, defined as the proportion of persons with a negative test result among persons who do not have the disease; it is calculated as follows: true negatives ÷ (true negatives + false positives). See also “Accuracy” and “Sensitivity”	REA	[1]
Stakeholder	An individual, organisation or initiative that participates in, is involved with, influences the outcomes of, or is impacted by the outcomes of, or implications of, a certain activity.	HTA decision-making	[17]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Standard gamble (SG)	A method of directly measuring the utility of a health status, founded on the fundamental von Neumann-Morgenstern axioms of expected utility theory. Note: A utility score is obtained by estimating the probabilities that a person who is asked to compare two options, one uncertain (the gamble), the other certain, will not prefer one over the other.	CEA	[1]
Standard marketing authorisation (EU)	SMA is a type of marketing authorisation that is granted by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) when comprehensive data are available that indicate a positive benefit-risk balance. Abbreviated as SMA.	Regulatory	[51]
Statistical significance	In hypothesis testing, a conclusion drawn when the null hypothesis is rejected, i.e. when the p-value is below the predetermined alpha level. See also “P-value”.	REA; CEA	[1]
Stochastic modelling	In the economic evaluation of healthcare interventions, stochastic uncertainty is one of a number of sources of uncertainty (others are parameter uncertainty, heterogeneity, and structural uncertainty), and it refers specifically to random variation in outcomes between identical patients. This is distinct from heterogeneity, which refers to variation between patients attributable to variations in the observed characteristics of those patients. Cohort state transition models (see Markov models) generally do not consider stochastic uncertainty (in their base case or sensitivity analyses); individual-level micro-simulation or discrete event simulation models will be needed if this is important.	CEA	[7]
Stochastic uncertainty	The random variability in outcomes between identical patients. Stochastic uncertainty has also been called first-order uncertainty or variability. See also “Random error”.	CEA	[41]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Strength of evidence	A measure of the overall confidence in the conclusions or recommendations of a systematic review, health technology assessment, or guidelines based on the quality of the evidence included.	REA; CEA	[1]
Structural uncertainty	Structural uncertainty is the uncertain error that results from using a model that is not a perfect representation of reality and therefore relates to the assumptions employed within the construction of a model	CEA	[52]
Subgroup analysis	A technique consisting of analysing the data from a subgroup separately from those from the overall population studied. Note: This type of analysis should be planned beforehand in the research protocol, and the results it provides are to be considered exploratory only. Any significant effect observed in a subgroup must be verified in other studies. See also “Multiple testing”.	REA; CEA	[1]
Surrogate outcome	A surrogate outcome is an outcome that is intended to replace an outcome of interest that cannot be observed in a trial. It is a variable that provides an indirect measurement of effect in situations in which direct measurement of a patient-centred effect is not feasible or practical. A surrogate outcome may be a biomarker that is intended to substitute for a patient-centred outcome, or it may be an intermediate outcome. A surrogate outcome is expected to only predict the treatment effect.	REA	[40]
Survival analysis	Survival analysis is an analytical method focusing on time-to-event data. Frequently, the event is death (overall survival), but many other events can be considered in this way, such as disease progression/relapse or event occurrence (for prevention).	REA	[7]
Systematic review	A form of structured literature review that addresses a question that is formulated to be answered by analysis of evidence and involves objective means of searching the literature, applying predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria to this literature, critically appraising the relevant literature, and extraction and synthesis of data from evidence base to formulate findings.	REA	[20]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Technology	<p>The application of scientific or other organised knowledge – relating to tools, techniques, products, processes, methods, modes of organisation, or systems – to practical tasks.</p> <p>Note: In health care, technology encompasses drugs; diagnostic tests, including indicators and reagents; devices; equipment and supplies; medical and surgical procedures; support systems; and organisational and managerial systems used in prevention, screening, diagnosis, treatment and rehabilitation.</p> <p>See also “Health technology”.</p>	Health Technology	[1]
Time Horizon	<p>The time horizon used for an economic evaluation is the duration over which health outcomes and costs are calculated.</p>	CEA	[7]
Time lag bias	<p>A form of bias due to the temporal limits of a literature search method likely to affect the inclusion of studies in a systematic review or any other form of literature synthesis.</p> <p>Note: Such bias may occur when the direction (positive or negative) or the strength (statistical significance) of a study’s results delays its publication.</p> <p>Alternate spelling: Time-lag bias.</p>	REA	[1]
Time series	<p>A series of measurements of the same variables taken over time.</p> <p>Note: A time series is said to be interrupted when a set of measurements is taken before an intervention is carried out or a change is made in a given system, and other measurements are taken over time after the change.</p>	REA	[1]
Time trade-off (TTO)	<p>A method for determining preference between two health states for different lengths of time, to estimate how many years of life a person is prepared to sacrifice to improve his/her health status.</p> <p>Note: For chronic states, the options are the reference health state for time t followed by death, or perfect health for a shorter time followed by death. For temporary states, the options are the reference health state for time t followed by an explicitly specified outcome (usually health), or a worse health state for a shorter time followed by the same outcome.</p>	CEA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
Transferability	<p>Transferability depends on context specificity; it refers to the ability to apply information and/or data from one HTA report into a report for the user’s target setting.</p> <p>Note: Generalisability and Transferability might be used with a similar but slightly different meaning. For example, ISPOR’s Good Research Practices Task Force wrote a guideline on the transferability of economic evaluations across jurisdictions and applied the following working definitions: “economic evaluations were generalizable if they applied, without adjustment, to other settings. On the other hand, data were transferable if they could be adapted to apply to other settings”.</p> <p>See also “External validity” and “Generalisability”</p>	REA; CEA	[27,28]
Transition probability	The probability that the health of a patient changes from one state to another within a given period.	CEA	[1]
Transportability	<p>Transportability refers to how well inferences generated from a sampled population may extend to a target population from which the original sample was not derived.</p> <p>See also “External validity” and “Generalisability”</p>	REA; CEA	[53]
Treatment effect	<p>The effect on the subjects’ health status or well-being attributable only to a treatment or intervention.</p> <p>Note: Investigators seek to estimate the true effect of a treatment or intervention by calculating the difference between the outcome obtained in the experimental group and the control group.</p> <p>See also “Effect size”.</p>	REA	[1]
Treatment switching	<p>Alteration of a patient’s treatment in a clinical trial where the patient discontinues their assigned treatment and commences an alternative treatment.</p> <p>Note 1: Treatment switching may be either a planned or unplanned part of a trial. Patients most commonly switch from the control group to the experimental treatment.</p>	REA	[1]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	<p>Note 2: The alternative treatment can include another trial treatment, a non-trial treatment, or no treatment.</p> <p>Synonyms include Treatment crossover.</p>		
Two-way sensitivity analysis	Two-way sensitivity analysis is a technique used in economic evaluation to assess the robustness of the overall result (typically of a model-based analysis) when simultaneously varying the values of two key input variables (parameters). This is particularly useful when there is a correlation between the two variables that are tested, in which case varying them independently in univariate sensitivity analyses may give a misleading view. Examples of such correlated input parameters might be hazard ratios for progression-free survival and overall survival for cancer therapy, or utility values for moderate and severe disease states.	CEA	[7]
Umbrella trial	To study multiple therapies in the context of a single disease. A master protocol designed to evaluate multiple investigational drugs administered as single drugs or as drug combinations in a single disease population. Clinical Trials Coordination Group define umbrella trials as trials that investigate the safety/efficacy/effects of several imps in a single population.	REA	[14]
Unit costs	Costs used in economic evaluation are often calculated as a product of counts of items of resource use associated with a patient’s care and a standard ‘unit’ cost of each type of item. In many healthcare systems, there are schedules of standard unit costs for different types of resource utilisation. Commonly used unit costs are for hospital in-patient care (per admission or per bed-day), intensive care (per day), emergency department outpatient, clinic or primary care (per visit), community nursing or therapy care (per hour), diagnostics (per test), medicines (per tablet or vial). The use of standard unit cost enables analysts to use the same sources for different economic evaluations, limiting one potential source of variability: if different costs are calculated for different interventions, this will be a result of differences in resources used rather than different valuations of each type of resource.	CEA	[7]

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Term	Definition	Taxonomy	Source
	Care should be taken when comparing unit costs across countries, as the definitions of resource items may vary.		
Univariate/one-way sensitivity analysis	Univariate/one-way sensitivity analysis allows a reviewer to assess the impact that changes in a certain input (parameter) will have on the output results of an economic evaluation (most frequently those based on a model) – this may be referred to as assessing the robustness of the result to that parameter. The parameter of interest should be varied between plausible extremes, preferably justified by a review of available evidence. This is the simplest form of sensitivity analysis since only one parameter is changed at one time, and correlations between parameters are not taken into account. Tornado diagrams are often used to summarise univariate sensitivity analyses testing a set of input variables in turn.	CEA	[7]
Utility	<p>1) In economic and decision analysis, the desirability of a specific health status or health outcome, usually expressed as being on a continuum from zero to one (death having a utility value of zero, and a full healthy life having a utility value of one).</p> <p>Note: This term is often used as a synonym for preference.</p> <p>2) The relative desirability of, or preference for, a specific health outcome or health status (usually from the perspective of the patient).</p>	CEA	[1]
Validity	<p>The ability of the result of a measurement or study to be accurate and free of bias (systematic errors).</p> <p>Note: In the context of a study, two types of validity are recognised: internal validity and external validity. In the context of measurement, there are several types of validity: construct validity, content validity, face validity, etc.</p>	REA; CEA	[1]
Value of information analysis	When used in health technology assessment, value of information (VOI) analysis is an umbrella term referring to the estimation of the value, in terms of cost and health outcomes, of collecting more data/information on key parameters influencing a decision, for example, reimbursement of a new technology. Typically, this is most useful where the output of an economic evaluation (e.g. incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER)) is	CEA	[7]

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	uncertain, yet close to a decision threshold (willingness to pay), and a key parameter on which the output is based is itself uncertain. As such, new information reducing uncertainty in that parameter will increase the chance of the correct decision being made, and the ‘value’ of this information is a function of how likely it would enable a decision to be made or changed. The usefulness of collecting information on parameters that have high certainty, or those which have a small bearing on the output of the economic evaluation, is likely to be low. VOI analysis may be particularly useful in assessing whether a further, expensive study is likely to yield helpful results (e.g., effectiveness). Common outputs of VOI analysis are the Expected Value of Perfect Information (EVPI), Expected Value of Partially Perfect Information (EVPPI) and Expected Value of Sample Information (EVSJ).		
Variable	A factor that can have different values. Note: The values measured in a study are data.	REA; CEA	[1]
Willingness-to-Pay (WTP)	The maximum amount that a person or an organisation is willing to pay: (a) to achieve a good health state or a particular outcome, or to increase its probability of occurrence; or (b) to avoid a bad health state or outcome, or to decrease its probability of occurrence.	CEA	[1]

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